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Modeling and control of MV converter

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary	15
2	Introduction	16
3	Isolated MPC building blocks	18
3.1	Smart transformers	18
3.1.1	Applications	18
3.1.2	Classification of STs	18
3.2	Dual active bridge	20
3.2.1	Modelling	21
3.3	Triple Active bridge	22
3.3.1	Description and model	22
3.3.2	Analysis and Modeling	23
3.3.3	Control Strategy	26
4	Modeling and control of isolated MPC	38
4.1	Definition of the topology	38
4.2	Modeling and control of building units	38
4.2.1	Multilevel converter	39
4.2.2	High-frequency isolation transformer	41
4.3	Operation of the multiport converter	43
4.3.1	Multiport converter configurations	44
4.3.2	Dynamic performance in normal conditions	44
4.3.3	Impact of modulation strategy	44
4.3.4	Impact of abnormal operation conditions	45
5	Modeling and control of non-isolated MPC	62
5.1	Definition of the topology	62
5.2	Modeling and control of building units	62
5.2.1	Centralized control	66
5.2.2	PLL	67
5.2.3	Reactive differential current calculation	67
5.2.4	Active differential current calculation	68
5.2.5	Inner current control	68
5.2.6	Energy calculation and control	69
5.2.7	Additive current reference calculation	70
5.2.8	Additive current control	70

5.2.9 Arms voltage calculation and modulation	71
5.2.10 Classical control structure	71
5.2.11 Crossed control structure	72
5.3 Modulation of the control signals	72
5.4 Impact of control strategies in abnormal conditions and AC faults	73
5.4.1 Classical control in both ports and an AC fault	74
5.4.2 Crossed control in both ports and an AC fault	75
5.4.3 Classical control in one port with AC fault near and Crossed control on the other port	75
5.5 Impact of control strategies in abnormal conditions and DC faults	76
5.5.1 Classical control	76
5.5.2 Crossed control	77
6 Application of grid-forming control in non-isolate MPC	83
6.1 Introduction	83
6.1.1 Active and reactive power decoupling methods	84
6.1.2 Considerations for a grid-forming multiport power converter	85
6.2 Methodology and modelling	86
6.2.1 Ideal voltage-source converter with grid-forming control	87
6.2.2 Non-isolated multiport power converter with grid-forming control	91
6.3 Impact of grid reactance to resistance ratio	94
6.3.1 Steady-state power transfer	94
6.3.2 Small-signal stability and dynamics	95
6.3.3 Current-limiting for the grid-forming converter	99
6.4 Initial analysis of the grid-forming multiport power converter	100
7 Conclusions	104

List of Acronyms

AC	Alternating current
CHB	Cascaded H – bridge
DAB	Dual active bridge
DC	Direct current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DN	Distribution network
EMT	Electro – magnetic transient
FB	Full(H) bridge
FF	Feed – forward
FRT	Fault ride through
GAM	Generalized average model
GFL	Grid following
GFM	Grid forming
HF	High frequency
HFT	High frequency transformer
HIL	Hardware in the loop
HV	High voltage
IGBT	Insulated – gate bipolar transistor
LV	Low voltage
MAB	Multi active bridge
MIMO	Multi – input multi – output
MMC	Modular multilevel converter
MPC	Multiport converter
MV	Medium voltage
NLM	Nearest level modulation
NMPZ	Non – minimum – phase zero
NPC	Neutral point clamped
PCC	Point of common coupling
PI	Proportional – integral
PSC	Phase shift carrier
PU	Per unit
PLL	Phase locked loop
PV	Photo voltaic
PWM	Pulse width modulation
RES	Renewable energy source
RHP	Right – half plane

SCR	Short circuit ratio
S&H	Sample and hold
SM	Sub module
SMC	Sliding mode controller
SOP	Soft open point
SPS	Singe phase shift
SRF	Synchronous reference frame
SSM	Small signal model
SST	Solid state transformer
ST	Smart transformer
STATCOM	Static synchronous compensator
SVPWM	Space vector pulse width modulation
TAB	Triple active bridge
VSC	Voltage source converter
VSI	Voltage source inverter
VSS	Variable structure system
VZ	Virtual impedance
X/R	reactance to resistance ratio

List of Nomenclatures

α_i	Weighting parameter
β	State matrix coefficient
C_{DC}	DC capacitor
C_{eq}	Equivalent capacitor
C_{SM}	Submodule capacitor
δ	Voltage angle difference
e	Error signal
F	Fault flag
F_s	Switching frequency
i_{DC}	DC current
i_l^j	Lower arm current
i_{non-pr}	Non – prioritized current
i_{PI}	Injected fault current
i_{pr}	Prioritized current
i_s	Grid current
i_{sum}	Additive current
i_u^j	Upper arm current
j	Imaginary number
L	Inductance
λ	Eigenvalue
m_i	Arm modulation index
μ	SMC control variable
N_{arm}	Submodules per arm
θ	Converter angle
ϕ	Phase shift angle
P	Active power
Q	Reactive power
R	Resistance
r_s	Parasitic resistance
S	Converter power
s	Switching function
σ	Sliding surface
T	MPC port
t	Time
τ	Integration period
u	PCC voltage

V_{conv}	Converter voltage
V_{Cl}^j	Applied lower arm voltage
V_{Cu}^j	Applied upper arm voltage
V_{dc}	DC port voltage
V_{diff}	Differential voltage
V_{l}^j	Lower arm voltage
V_{SM}	SM capacitor voltage
V_{sum}	Additive voltage
V_{u}^j	Upper arm voltage
X	Reactance
x	State variable
W	Energy
ω	Converter angular velocity

List of Figures

1	(a) Triple Active Bridge DC-DC converter. (b) Y-type primary-referred equivalent circuit. (c) Δ -type primary-referred equivalent circuit.	23
2	Transformer voltage and current waveforms.	24
3	Output voltage response under load and input voltage disturbances in port 2	31
4	Output voltage response under load and input voltage disturbances in port 3	31
5	Simplified equivalent TAB DC-DC converter referred to port 1.	32
6	Block diagram of Control scheme.	35
7	Response of the TAB converter under nominal operation conditions: (a) Total power in each port, (b) Output voltages at Port 2 and Port 3.	36
8	Response of the TAB converter under input voltage and loads disturbances: (a) Total power in each port, (b) Output voltages at Port 2 and Port 3.	37
9	Waveforms of phase shift before and after three consecutive disturbances . . .	37
10	Schematic of isolated MPC configuration	38
11	Detailed schematic of two alternative implementation of one phase of the isolated MPC configuration.	39
12	Detailed schematic of a 3-phase MMC with N CHB-based submodules.	40
13	Schematic of a multi-active bridge DC-DC converter unit.	42
14	power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through windings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter.	45
15	DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage.	46
16	Carrier (top) signals to generate the PWM output voltage (bottom) of the MMC for phase a.	47
17	Carrier (top) signals to generate the PWM output voltage (bottom) of the MMC for phase a.	47
18	Bipolar switching MAB operation; input voltage to the winding 1 and 3 of the MAB (top), the corresponding differential voltage on the leakage inductance (middle) and the resulting current on winding 1 (bottom).	48
19	variation of harmonics content with zero voltage output for an angle of α for half the period; voltage waveform with uni-polar switching (top) and harmonics content (bottom).	49

20 Uni-polar switching MAB operation with $\alpha = 45$ deg; input voltage to the winding 1 and 3 of the MAB (top), the corresponding differential voltage on the leakage inductance (middle) and the resulting current on winding 1 (bottom). 50

21 power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through winings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter. ac-port 1 is disconnected at 0.55 sec. 51

22 DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage. ac-port 1 is disconnected at 0.55 sec. 52

23 Grid voltage when a 3-phase voltage-dip occurs at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec. . . . 53

24 power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through winings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter; a 3-phase voltage-dip happened at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec and P_{ref} is set to $-P_{dc,port}$ 54

25 DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage; a 3-phase voltage-dip happened at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec and P_{ref} is set to $-P_{dc,port}$ 55

26 An unbalanced grid-voltage ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec. 56

27 power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through windings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter; an unbalanced grid-voltage at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec. 57

28 DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage; an unbalanced grid-voltage at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec. 58

29 active power and current in the input side of the MAB module; winding 2 is open for 0.2 - 0.22 sec. 59

30 power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-
power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through winings 1,
2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at
ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter.
winding 2 of one MAB module open for 0.2 - 0.22 sec. 60

31 DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor
voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM
capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage. winding 2 of
one MAB open for 0.2-0.22 sec. 61

32 General schematic of the presented MPC. 62

33 General schematic of the MPC control. 62

34 Equivalent circuit of a three-phase MMC. 63

35 Average model representation of an MMC [1]. 64

36 General control of an MMC. 65

37 Centralized control. 66

38 PLL. 67

39 Reactive differential current block. 68

40 Arm energy calculation [2]. 69

41 Energy balancing control [2]. 69

42 Additive current reference calculation [2]. 70

43 Additive current control [2]. 71

44 Arms voltage calculation and modulation [2]. 71

45 Classical control i_{sum}^{0dc*} calculation [1]. 72

46 Crossed control structure [1]. 72

47 Modulation techniques for a MMC [3]. 73

48 System studied with AC balanced faults. 74

49 Port 1 results and classical control. 75

50 Port 2 results and classical control. 76

51 Port 1 results, classical control and switching model. 77

52 Port 2 results, classical control and switching model. 78

53 Port 1 results and crossed control. 78

54 Port 2 results and crossed control. 79

55 Port 1 results, crossed control and switching model. 79

56 Port 2 results, crossed control and switching model. 80

57 Port 1 (Crossed) results and combined control. 80

58 Port 2 (Classical) results and combined control. 81

59 System studied with DC fault. 81

60	Port 1 results, crossed control and DC fault.	82
61	Port 2 results, crossed control and DC fault.	82
62	An overview of the features of approaches to decouple active and reactive power in low to mid X/R derived from the literature review. Green indicates a desirable characteristic, while yellow indicates mediocre, and red indicates undesirable. No colour is assigned if the approach does not have a clear impact on the given feature.	84
63	Single line diagram of the non-isolated multiport power converter with one grid-forming and one grid-following port connected to two AC feeders and the distant grid. The DC port integrates a battery.	86
64	Line diagram of ideal VSC used for analysis of GFM control in low to mid X/R conditions.	87
65	Grid-forming control diagram.	89
66	Verification of MIMO SSM active and reactive power responses to a 1 % step in the active power reference as the grid’s X/R ratio and the converter’s initial power operating point are varied.	90
67	Verification of MIMO SSM current responses to a 1 % step in the active grid voltage component as the grid’s X/R ratio and the converter’s initial power operating point are varied.	91
68	Verification of MIMO SSM current responses to a 1 % step in the reactive grid voltage component as the grid’s X/R ratio and the converter’s initial power operating point are varied.	92
69	Battery circuit diagram.	93
70	DC battery port control diagram.	93
71	DC link circuit of the non-isolated MPC.	94
72	Steady-state active and reactive power transfer as a function of converter angle as grid X/R ratio varies.	95
73	Verification of active power transfer capability on different grid X/R ratios using the EMT TDM.	96
74	Participation factors of the linearised closed loop VSC and grid system for an initial inversion operating point $P_0 = -0.9 PU$, on three example grid X/R ratios.	96
75	Pole-zero map of the linearised model for an initial inversion operating point $P_0 = -0.9 PU$ as X/R varies. Subplot a) exhibits the widest scale (excluding neglected modes), b) exhibits a zoom to mid-scale, c) exhibits a zoom to narrow scale, d) focuses on poles 13,14, and e) focuses on poles 18, 19, and 20.	98

76 Time-domain active and reactive power responses of the converter in response to an active power reference step of -10 % for an initial inversion operating point $P_0 = -0.9 \text{ PU}$ and a range of grid X/R ratios. 98

77 Verification of the GFM’s current limiting capability using the EMT TDM. 99

78 Verification of the GFM with current-limiting virtual impedance’s active power transfer capability on different grid X/R ratios using the EMT TDM. 100

79 Verification of the MPC’s active power transfer capability on different grid X/R ratios using the EMT TDM. This case dispatches the GFM port to invert power and the GFL port to rectify power. 101

80 Focus on the time-domain properties of the MPC during the final power step pictured in Fig.79. 101

81 The MPC’s current-limiting ability following a three phase fault on the AC grid for a case where the GFM port is inverting $P = -0.5\text{PU}$ and the GFL is rectifying $P = 0.5\text{PU}$ 102

82 The MPC’s current-limiting ability following a three phase fault on the AC grid for a case where the GFM port is inverting $P = -0.1\text{PU}$ and the GFL is rectifying $P = 0.1\text{PU}$ 103

List of Tables

1	TAB parameters	30
2	TAB Converter parameters	36
3	Converter current components and their uses.	64
4	Parameters used for the simulations.	74
5	Base GFM tuning and ideal VSC model parameters.	88
6	Model parameters for the non-isolated MPC with GFM port.	94

1 Executive summary

This report, Deliverable 2.1 of the iPLUG project, overviews the work that has been carried out in WP2 on modeling and control of multiport power converters (MPCs) for medium voltage application. The report details on the modeling, simulation and testing of two distinct MPC topologies, isolated and non-isolated alternatives. Circuitual structures of the two topologies and a detailed description of the building units that make up the converter are described. The dynamic performance of the topologies in normal and abnormal conditions are also demonstrated. In the case of non-isolated topology, the application of grid-forming control and the challenges associated with it has been highlighted. Key advantages and challenges associated with each topology will also be briefly discussed as an initial input for the next task in the work package on topology evaluation for laboratory validation.

2 Introduction

In Line with the EU's commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement, modern power systems are increasingly dominated by clean energy sources with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions to achieve the aim of being climate-neutral by 2050. Hence, there is an unquestionable trend to increase the penetration of renewables to unprecedented levels both at transmission and distribution level. In this regard, European Union is targeting a 40% share of renewables by 2030 with the intention to achieve much higher targets by 2050. With this effort in the transition towards more renewable energy production, the use of power-electronic converters to interface these sources to the grid is correspondingly increasing. The type and level of these renewable sources is high specially at distribution level and hence the demand for power-electronic based solutions to increase the capacity and reliability of the grid is even more important.

At distribution level with significant penetration of renewable sources (such as solar PV and wind power plants), several industrial loads, electrical vehicle charging stations, and energy storage units, power electronics play a vital role in enhancing integration of renewables and energy storage systems, optimal use of the distribution network, and connection of various loads at different voltage levels both with AC and DC. Some of the power-electronic solutions discussed in the literature in the distribution grid for capacity enhancement, improved flexibility, and better controllability include the use of Soft-Open Point (SOP), smart transformers and multiport converters [4–6]. When isolation is required in some of these configurations for medium/high voltage applications and when varying voltage levels are involved, high-frequency based DC-DC converters are important building blocks of the converters. In this regard, dual-active bridge (DAB) based DC-DC converter is the most common configuration. On the other hand, the use of DC-DC converters with multiple active-bridges has the advantage of reliability during faults and reduce the number of modules for medium/high power application [7, 8]. In line with this, WP2 aims to develop suitable multiport converter topologies and their control schemes to enhance MV distribution system's efficiency and utilization. Different multiport converter structures will be investigated and ranked, based on the specific functionalities to be provided to the distribution grid. To achieve this objective, modeling, and control of multiport power converters for medium voltage application has been discussed in this report, where two distinct MPC topologies, isolated and non-isolated alternatives have been considered. The various components that make up the converters are described and the operation of the converters in different operation conditions have also been demonstrated. In this report, tasks 2.1 and 2.2 of WP2 have been documented and a summary of the work include:

1. Modeling and simulation of multiport converter for MV applications

- Literature review of existing solutions such as dedicated converter per port, soft-open points (SOP), and smart transformers (ST) to motivate the benefits of multiport converter (MPC) solutions.
- Development of Simulation models of MPCs using multilevel converters (MMC) as building blocks for medium voltage (MV).
- Two categories, one with no-isolation between the ports and one with full isolation between the ports (ST as starting points), have been developed. In each category, variations of implementation based on the type of sub-module (half- or full-bridge modules) for the MMC or the type of isolation (dual-, triple- or multi-active bridge DC-DC converters) have been studied. The modeling detail includes both average models and detailed switching models. In all cases, two medium voltage ac ports and a dc-port for energy storage or PV-integration have been considered.

2. Development of control and modulation strategies for multiport converters

- A multiport converter with two ac-ports and one dc-port has been developed. All controllers such as current controller, direct-voltage or energy controllers, ac-voltage or reactive-power controller and phase-locked loop (PLL) as well as the low-level controller's capacitor balancing, and modulation have been implemented and tested. In the case of isolated MPC, two modulation strategies have been developed for the MMCs and control of dual-, triple- and multi-active bridge DC-DC converters which acts as building modules for MV application is developed.
- Literature review of grid-forming characteristics of converters in case of low X/R grid connection (such as active- and reactive-power coupling, dynamic performance, and necessary trade-offs) and development of this control into MPCs.
- Dynamic performance of the implemented MPC converter control and modulation has been tested in the case of normal conditions (harmonic performance, speed of response) and abnormal conditions (ac/dc faults, loss of a module).

3 Isolated MPC building blocks

In this chapter, the isolated DC-DC converters used in the MPC will be the subject of study. A brief introduction to the Smart transformer and its conversion stages is presented. Furthermore, the isolated DC-DC topology is presented. The dual active bridge is introduced, and two modeling and control strategies are proposed for the triple active bridge (TAB).

3.1 Smart transformers

Solid State Transformers (SSTs), leveraging power electronic components and high-frequency transformers, have emerged as promising alternatives to conventional low-frequency transformers. They offer advantages such as reduced volume, weight, and enhanced controllability. Building upon the foundation of SSTs, smart transformers (STs) represent a significant evolution, integrating advanced functionalities to provide ancillary services to distribution and transmission grids [9]. This section explores the functionalities, applications, and key components of STs, with a focus on their role in enabling the energy transition and optimizing grid operations.

3.1.1 Applications

STs play a pivotal role in supporting the energy transition by enabling a range of applications that conventional low-frequency transformers cannot fulfill [10]. These include:

- Integration of DC microgrids with distributed energy sources (DERs) between medium voltage (MV) and low voltage (LV) grids through the DC link. In this case, ST acts as a three-port power router. This facilitates renewable energy sources (RES) integration and grid services provision through optimal power flow control.
- Ancillary services provision. Voltage regulation, reactive power compensation, and harmonic filtering, thereby replacing bulky conventional transformers coupled with Static Synchronous Compensators (STATCOMs), traditionally employed in large wind power plants.
- Isolation and fault limitation, leveraging advanced control capabilities to enhance grid resilience.

3.1.2 Classification of STs

STs are mainly classified on the number of conversion stages. These stages include the single-stage, two-stage, and three-stage configurations, each offering distinct characteristics and functionalities [11].

Single-stage ST These STs are characterized by higher power density and the absence of DC-link capacitors. They typically employ a direct isolated matrix converter. However, a notable limitation of this setup is the lack of decoupling between the LV and MV sides, constraining the control capabilities. While advantageous in terms of compactness, the single-stage configuration may face challenges in achieving optimal control and versatility due to the intertwined nature of LV and MV components.

Two-stages ST In contrast, the two-stage ST often adopts an indirect matrix converter combined with an inverter. This arrangement introduces at least one constant DC-link, enhancing control capabilities compared to the single-stage setup. Despite this improvement, the two-stage configuration may exhibit limitations in terms of functionalities. While it provides a degree of separation between LV and MV components, it may not offer the same level of control flexibility as the three-stage counterpart.

Three-stages ST The three-stage configuration represents a comprehensive approach, incorporating a MV AC-DC converter, an isolated DC-DC converter, and a LV inverter. This topology typically features two constant DC-links, with at least one available for connectivity purposes. The pivotal aspect of the three-stage configuration lies in the decoupling between MV and LV sides. This separation facilitates the implementation of diverse functionalities tailored to grid requirements.

The following paragraphs describe each of these stages:

MV AC-DC converter The MV AC-DC conversion stage serves as the initial step in the transformation process within STs. Among the available options, multilevel converters, particularly Modular Multi-level converters (MMC) and Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB) converters stand out for their technical suitability and versatility in grid applications.

MMC and CHB converters offer several advantages, including modularity, potential fault-tolerant implementation, reduced electromagnetic interference, and compact filter size. However, CHB converters present distinct features that make them particularly well-suited for smart transformer applications [8]:

- CHB converters require fewer modules compared to MMCs, resulting in fewer semiconductor and auxiliary components. This reduction in component count translates to cost savings and enhanced reliability.
- The total capacitance in CHB converters is significantly lower than in MMCs, leading to a smaller overall size.
- Control implementation in CHB converters is comparatively easier than in MMCs, enhancing operational efficiency and reliability.

Isolated DC-DC converter The isolated DC-DC conversion stage plays a crucial role in ensuring power transfer between the MV and LV sides of the smart transformer, serving as an intermediary step in voltage transformation. Key requirements for this stage include [8]:

- High voltage isolation from MV to LV.
- Robustness to high voltages in the MV side and high currents in the LV side.
- Decoupling between the MV and the LV port: meaning that providing ancillary service to a network does not affect the other.
- High conversion efficiency to avoid energy losses.
- Bidirectional and controllable power flow to facilitate the integration of an increasing amount of renewable energy sources.

Various converter options, such as active bridges, resonant converters, and full-bridge DC-DC converters, fulfill these requirements, offering flexibility and adaptability to diverse grid environments and operating conditions. Among these, multi-active bridges emerge as a promising choice due to their versatility, efficiency, and scalability.

This stage is a fundamental difference of ST when compared to other MV converters such as the MMC converter. DC-AC cells supply a high-frequency transformer with typical two-winding or multiple windings connected to its core. The last is an interesting option for multiport converters, due to its ability to interconnect different DERs that operate at different voltages through the ST. Furthermore, multi-winding isolation expands the topology options of the isolated converter to symmetrical/asymmetrical topologies that could increase the power density and reduce the cost of the solution.

Low voltage inverter The final stage of smart transformer operation requires a low-voltage inverter. Topologies commonly employed for this stage include two-level voltage source inverters (VSI), three-level neutral point clamped (NPC), and T-type topologies. The main design considerations for this stage are the robustness to LV disturbances and the optimal sizing of the filter. Additionally, the converter at this stage should be able to withstand unbalanced conditions and non-linear loads.

3.2 Dual active bridge

As a fundamental component of the STs, the active bridges are analyzed in the next sections, with a particular focus on the Triple Active Bridge (TAB), for which novel models and control techniques have been developed in the framework of iPLUG project.

Since the TAB and Multiple Active Bridge (MAB) converters are extensions of the Dual Active Bridge (DAB), the DAB operation principle and modeling is summarized before delving

into the work carried out on TAB modeling and control. The DAB, introduced in [12], is an isolated, bidirectional, and highly efficient DC-DC converter. It is composed of two identical primary and secondary side full-bridge converters, connected through a high-frequency transformer. The DAB operation and power flow are controlled mainly using a delay in the commutation of the AC signals in the primary and secondary full-bridge converters. This delay is known as phase-shift since both full-bridges are operated at the same switching frequency, and the modulation strategy is known as single-phase-shift modulation. The modulation of the duty cycle in each full-bridge converter could be used in the DAB control, which could be beneficial for expanding the zero-voltage-switching operation range. The last modulation strategy is known as dual-phase-shift and triple-phase-shift.

3.2.1 Modelling

Modeling the DAB is more challenging than non-isolated converters, since one of the state variables, i.e. the inductor current in the transformer i_L is AC, with an average value 0. Three different modeling approaches are summarized here. The three methodologies can be employed for different modulation techniques (single, double, or triple phase shift) [13].

Reduced order model In this model, the dynamics of i_L are ignored and the remaining variables are described by averaging over a switching period. The reduced order model for single phase shift modulated DAB leads to the following expression of the output power.

$$P = \frac{Nv_1v_2\phi(1-2|\phi|)}{f_sL} \quad (1)$$

where N is the turns ratio, v_1 and v_2 are the input and output port voltages, ϕ is the phase shift between the switches at the primary and secondary, f_s the switching frequency and L the transformer leakage inductance.

Full-order model To obtain a full-order model of the DAB, the Generalized Average Model (GAM) can be used. In this model approach, the dynamic of i_L is included and some authors have used this to depict new control strategies [14]. It is based on the Fourier series expansion of a signal $x(\tau)$ on the interval $\tau \in [t-T, t]$ [15], that will be described in more detail in Section 3.3.3 of this deliverable.

Discrete-time model The discrete-time model uses the different switching states in a switching cycle to describe the dynamics of the whole system. In this case, the variables describing the state of the system are not continuous functions of time $x(t)$, but discrete vectors $x[k]$. This method provides very accurate results, it can easily consider the zero

voltage switching, delays, and high-order harmonics. The main drawback is its large computational burden, which makes it unfeasible for power system studies with a large number of elements included in a power grid.

For these models, the small-signal version can be obtained by introducing a small perturbation and linearizing the systems around the equilibrium point.

3.3 Triple Active bridge

3.3.1 Description and model

As the integration of multiple power electronics-based resources usually requires several power converters (one converter per asset as a general rule), multiport converters are of great interest given their improved efficiency, power density, cost, energy management, etc.

The triple-active bridge converter follows many operation principles and features from the dual-active bridge converter. The DAB principles are extended to a three-port converter, where each port is isolated. The main inherited features are listed below.

- Isolation is achieved using a high-frequency transformer.
- High voltage gain thanks to the transformer turn ratio between ports.
- Bidirectional power flow control through the phase difference between port or phase shift.
- Zero-voltage switching capability in a range of operation points.

Despite the operational similarities of the TAB with the DAB, however, the complexity of the TAB converter is higher due to magnetic coupling between ports, making the power flow decoupling one of the main challenges.

This unique challenge has been investigated in the literature leading to common solutions like:

- Model-based feed-forward control.
- Time-sharing decoupling.
- Robust nonlinear control (Model-based predictive control, sliding mode control, etc.).

Moreover, these methods' efficacy depends on a mathematical model of the TAB. The next subsection analyzes the operation of the TAB and presents the mathematical fundamentals that are used to model the TAB. Furthermore, two methodologies are investigated to depict model-based control strategies for the TAB. First, the generalized average model

(GAM) approach is considered to model and analyze the operation of the triple active bridge. The model obtained with the GAM is used to depict a control strategy based on linear feedback + feedback control. Later, a nonlinear control strategy based on a reduced order model and a sliding mode control is presented. Moreover, the results of both methodologies are discussed.

3.3.2 Analysis and Modeling

The circuit representing a TAB is shown in Fig. 1(a). It consists of a three-winding high-frequency transformer connecting three full-bridge DC-AC converters. Each port p is characterized by a collective parasitic resistance r_{sp} , a total leakage inductance L_p , a full-bridge converter, a filter capacitor C_p , and a load resistance R_p .

Without loss of generality, the port 1 is chosen as a reference and in this way, its associated phase shift ϕ_1 is considered 0. Furthermore, the magnetic inductance of the transformer is assumed to be much greater than the leakage inductance and therefore can be ignored. The Y -type and Δ -type primary-referred equivalent circuits of the TAB converter are shown in Fig. 1(b) and Fig. 1(c).

Figure 1: (a) Triple Active Bridge DC-DC converter. (b) Y-type primary-referred equivalent circuit. (c) Δ -type primary-referred equivalent circuit.

The following assumptions are made to develop a tractable model of the TAB while

Figure 2: Transformer voltage and current waveforms.

guaranteeing the level of accuracy required for control design purposes:

- The switches are considered ideal: switching transients are negligible and dead time is not taken into account.
- The voltage drop across transistor-diode pairs is neglected.
- The dynamics of the input capacitor are not considered due to the large input capacitance C_{in} .

Fig. 2 presents the transformer voltage and current waveforms during one period cycle. The waveforms show the six switching transitions during one commutation period of the TAB converter. By considering the transformer inductance currents (i_1, i_2) and the output capacitor voltages (v_2, v_3) as state variables, the switched model of the TAB converter can be easily obtained by applying Kirchhoff's laws:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dv_2(t)}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{C_2 R_2} v_2(t) - \frac{u_2(t)}{C_2} i_2(t) \\
 \frac{di_2(t)}{dt} &= -\frac{r_{s2}}{L_2} i_2(t) + \frac{u_2(t)}{L_2} v_2(t) - \frac{n_2}{L_2} v_{tr}(t) \\
 \frac{dv_3(t)}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{C_3 R_3} v_3(t) - \frac{u_3(t)}{C_3} i_3(t) \\
 \frac{di_3(t)}{dt} &= -\frac{r_{s3}}{L_3} i_3(t) + \frac{u_3(t)}{L_3} v_3(t) - \frac{n_3}{L_3} v_{tr}(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

This set of equations can be written compactly as:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{s}) \tag{3}$$

where x is the set of state variables, $u_i(t)$ represents the switching operation of each full bridge, and s the set of switching functions with period T .

The power flowing between the ports of a generic active bridge can be controlled using different variables:

- The phase shift between two ports.
- The duty cycle of the full-bridge converters.
- The switching frequency.

In this case, the single-phase-shift (SPS) modulation is considered, and the duty cycle and frequency are assumed to be constant values at 50% and f_s , respectively. Therefore, the power transfer between two ports can be computed as:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}v_i v_j}{\omega_s L_{ij}} \phi_{ij} \left(\pi - \frac{|\phi_{ij}|}{\pi} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\phi_{ij} = \phi_j - \phi_i$ is the phase shift angle and its sign determines the direction of power flow. In (4), v_i is the voltage at port i , v_j the voltage at port j , where ω_s the switching frequency, n_{ij} the turn ratio of the j -th port with respect to the i -th port, and L_{ij} the equivalent leakage inductance between port i and j defined by (5).

$$L_{ij} = L'_i + L'_j + \frac{L'_i L'_j}{L'_k}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad \text{and} \quad k \neq i, j \quad (5)$$

where L'_i is the leakage inductance at each port i reflected to port 1 ($L'_i = L_i n_{1,i}^2$).

Furthermore, the power in each port is defined as

$$P_i = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^3 P_{ij} \quad (6)$$

For simplicity, it is assumed that the power flow goes from port 1 to ports 2 and 3 where $\phi_3 > \phi_2 > \phi_1$. The power expressions become as

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= P_{12} + P_{13} \\ P_2 &= -P_{12} + P_{23} \\ P_3 &= -P_{13} - P_{23} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

According to the energy conservation law, the power generated by port 1 should be the sum of the powers absorbed by ports 2 and 3. In other words, the total power should be equal to zero.

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 P_i = 0 \quad (8)$$

3.3.3 Control Strategy

As shown in the previous subsection, the TAB converter is a switched nonlinear and coupled circuit. The power flow decoupling represents a major challenge in the control design. In this section, the design process of two controllers is presented. The first one is a linear feedback and feed-forward (FF) proportional-integral (PI) controller and the second one is a nonlinear sliding mode controller (SMC).

Feedback proportional-integral controller The design of this controller is based on a linearized model of the switching model presented in (2). First, an average model is derived using the GAM. Then, the average model obtained is linearized around the operating point to obtain a linear time-invariant model.

Average model This subsection describes the mathematical model of the TAB obtained using the GAM [16]. The GAM is a well-known method that has been used to represent the dynamics of power converters [17]. This approach allows full-order mathematical representation of power converter topologies where AC signals appear and the typical small-ripple approximation is not valid. Since this is the case of active bridge converters, the GAM is investigated here. Authors in [16] and [18] presented the GAM of the TAB. These works showed a methodology to obtain the average and small-signal model using the first harmonic approximation. Furthermore, the authors validated the proposed model by comparing its frequency response to that of a prototype, which confirmed the usefulness of the GAM technique in representing the dynamic response of the TAB.

The GAM was proposed in [17] to extend the possibility of deriving averaged models to converters containing AC stages. This method could be used to obtain an average model of the TAB, which could be linearized and used to derive control strategies using classical linear control theory.

The GAM is based on the approximation of state variables through their complex Fourier series representation in the interval $t - T \leq \tau \leq T$ [19]:

$$x(\tau) = \sum_k \langle x \rangle_k(t) e^{jk\omega_s \tau} \quad (9)$$

where $\omega_s = \frac{2\pi}{T}$ and the k_{th} coefficient of the Fourier transform is

$$\langle x \rangle_k(t) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t-T}^T x(\tau) e^{-jk\omega_s \tau} d\tau \quad (10)$$

Two main properties of Fourier coefficients are useful for the application of the GAM to the TAB:

1. Differentiation with respect to time:

$$\frac{d\langle x \rangle_k(t)}{dt} = \left\langle \frac{dx}{dt} \right\rangle_k(t) - jk\omega_s \langle x \rangle_k(t) \quad (11)$$

2. Convolutional relationship between coefficients:

$$\langle xy \rangle_k(t) = \sum_i \langle x \rangle_{k-i} \langle y \rangle_i \quad (12)$$

A good compromise between the accuracy and complexity of the model can be reached by considering only the first-order harmonic [19]. In the following equations, the subscripts 0 and 1 refer to the zero and first harmonic coefficient of the Fourier series.

To obtain a GAM of the TAB, first, the relevant Fourier coefficients of both sides of each equation of (3) are computed as

$$\left\langle \frac{dx}{dt} \right\rangle_k = \langle f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \rangle_k \quad (13)$$

Then, applying the differentiation property, (13) becomes

$$\frac{d\langle x \rangle_k(t)}{dt} = -jk\omega_s \langle x \rangle_k(t) + \langle f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \rangle_k \quad (14)$$

Considering that $\langle x \rangle_0 = 0$ for AC waveforms, $\langle x \rangle_1 = 0$ for DC waveforms, and a duty cycle equal to 50%, the following Fourier coefficients are all zero if their initial values are zero:

$$\left[\langle u_1 \rangle_0, \langle u_2 \rangle_0, \langle u_3 \rangle_0, \langle i_2 \rangle_0, \langle i_3 \rangle_0, \langle v_2 \rangle_1, \langle v_3 \rangle_1 \right] \quad (15)$$

Then, the system of equations in (13) is expanded to (16).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \langle v_2 \rangle_0 &= -\frac{1}{C_2 R_2} \langle v_2 \rangle_0 - \frac{2}{C_2} \langle u_2 \rangle_{1R} \langle i_2 \rangle_{1R} - \frac{2}{C_2} \langle u_2 \rangle_{1I} \langle i_2 \rangle_{1I} \\ \frac{d}{dt} \langle i_2 \rangle_{1R} &= -\frac{r_{s2}}{L_2} \langle i_2 \rangle_{1R} + \omega_s \langle i_2 \rangle_{1I} + \frac{\langle u_2 \rangle_{1R}}{L_2} \langle v_2 \rangle_0 - \frac{n_2}{L_2} \langle v_{tr} \rangle_{1R} \\ \frac{d}{dt} \langle i_2 \rangle_{1I} &= -\frac{r_{s2}}{L_2} \langle i_2 \rangle_{1I} - \omega_s \langle i_2 \rangle_{1R} + \frac{\langle u_2 \rangle_{1I}}{L_2} \langle v_2 \rangle_0 - \frac{n_2}{L_2} \langle v_{tr} \rangle_{1I} \\ \frac{d}{dt} \langle v_3 \rangle_0 &= -\frac{1}{C_3 R_3} \langle v_3 \rangle_0 - \frac{2}{C_3} \langle u_3 \rangle_{1R} \langle i_3 \rangle_{1R} - \frac{2}{C_3} \langle u_3 \rangle_{1L} \langle i_3 \rangle_{1I} \\ \frac{d}{dt} \langle i_3 \rangle_{1R} &= -\frac{r_{s3}}{L_3} \langle i_3 \rangle_{1R} + \omega_s \langle i_3 \rangle_{1I} + \frac{\langle u_3 \rangle_{1R}}{L_3} \langle v_3 \rangle_0 - \frac{n_3}{L_3} \langle v_{tr} \rangle_{1R} \\ \frac{d}{dt} \langle i_3 \rangle_{1I} &= -\frac{r_{s3}}{L_3} \langle i_3 \rangle_{1I} - \omega_s \langle i_3 \rangle_{1R} + \frac{\langle u_3 \rangle_{1I}}{L_3} \langle v_3 \rangle_0 - \frac{n_3}{L_3} \langle v_{tr} \rangle_{1I} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Considering a constant duty cycle of 50% in the three active bridges, the Fourier coefficients of the switching functions u_1 , u_2 , and u_3 are presented in (17). Moreover, an expression for the transformer windings' voltage v_{tr} is derived using the principle of super-

position assuming a linear behavior in the transformer, leaving the expression presented in (18).

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_1 \rangle_{1R} &= 0 & \langle u_1 \rangle_{1I} &= -\frac{2}{\pi} & \langle u_2 \rangle_{1R} &= -\frac{2 \sin \phi_2}{\pi} \\ \langle u_2 \rangle_{1I} &= -\frac{2 \cos \phi_2}{\pi} & \langle u_3 \rangle_{1R} &= -\frac{2 \sin \phi_3}{\pi} & \langle u_3 \rangle_{1I} &= -\frac{2 \cos \phi_3}{\pi} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle v_{tr} \rangle_{1R} &= \frac{2l_{2I}}{\pi} V_1 + \frac{2}{\pi} (l_{3I} \cos \phi_2 - l_{3R} \sin \phi_2) \frac{\langle v_2 \rangle_0}{n_2} + \frac{2}{\pi} (l_{1I} \cos \phi_3 - l_{1R} \sin \phi_3) \frac{\langle v_3 \rangle_0}{n_3} \\ \langle v_{tr} \rangle_{1I} &= -\frac{2l_{2R}}{\pi} V_1 - \frac{2}{\pi} (l_{3R} \cos \phi_2 + l_{3I} \sin \phi_2) \frac{\langle v_2 \rangle_0}{n_2} - \frac{2}{\pi} (l_{1R} \cos \phi_3 + l_{1I} \sin \phi_3) \frac{\langle v_3 \rangle_0}{n_3} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Finally, substituting (17) and (18) in (16), and linearizing the system considering small perturbations around the operating point, the final system of linear equations is shown in (19), where the R and I subscripts indicate the real and imaginary parts of the Fourier coefficients and the coefficients m_1, \dots, m_8 and $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{10}$ depend on the physical parameters and the operating point of the TAB as presented in (20)

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{20} \\ \hat{i}_{21R} \\ \hat{i}_{21I} \\ \hat{v}_{30} \\ \hat{i}_{31R} \\ \hat{i}_{31I} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{C_2 R_2} & \frac{4 \sin \phi_2}{\pi C_2} & \frac{4 \cos \phi_2}{\pi C_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m_1 & -\frac{r_{s2}}{L_2} & \omega_S & m_2 & 0 & 0 \\ m_3 & -\omega_s & -\frac{-r_{s2}}{L_2} & m_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{C_3 R_3} & \frac{4 \sin \phi_3}{\pi C_3} & \frac{4 \cos \phi_3}{\pi C_3} \\ m_5 & 0 & 0 & m_6 & -\frac{r_{s3}}{L_3} & \omega_S \\ m_7 & 0 & 0 & m_8 & -\omega_S & -\frac{r_{s3}}{L_3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{20} \\ \hat{i}_{21R} \\ \hat{i}_{21I} \\ \hat{v}_{30} \\ \hat{i}_{31R} \\ \hat{i}_{31I} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 & 0 \\ \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ \beta_4 & \beta_5 \\ 0 & \beta_6 \\ \beta_7 & \beta_8 \\ \beta_9 & \beta_{10} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\phi}_2 \\ \hat{\phi}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= \frac{2}{\pi L_2} \{ (l_{3R} - 1) \sin \phi_2 - l_{3I} \cos \phi_2 \}, & m_2 &= \frac{2n_2}{\pi L_2 n_3} \{ l_{1R} \sin \phi_3 - l_{1I} \cos \phi_3 \} \\ m_3 &= \frac{2}{\pi L_2} \{ l_{3I} \sin \phi_2 + (l_{3R} - 1) \cos \phi_2 \}, & m_4 &= \frac{2n_2}{\pi L_2 n_3} \{ l_{1I} \sin \phi_3 + l_{1R} \cos \phi_3 \} \\ m_5 &= \frac{2n_3}{\pi L_3 n_2} \{ l_{3R} \sin \phi_2 - l_{3I} \cos \phi_2 \}, & m_6 &= \frac{2}{\pi L_3} \{ (l_{1R} - 1) \sin \phi_3 - l_{1I} \cos \phi_3 \} \\ m_7 &= \frac{2n_3}{\pi L_3 n_2} \{ l_{3I} \sin \phi_2 + l_{3R} \cos \phi_2 \}, & m_8 &= \frac{2}{\pi L_3} \{ l_{1I} \sin \phi_3 + (l_{1R} - 1) \cos \phi_3 \} \\ \beta_1 &= \frac{4}{\pi C_2} \{ I_{21R} \cos \phi_2 - I_{21I} \sin \phi_2 \}, & \beta_2 &= \frac{2V_{20}}{\pi L_2} \{ (l_{3R} - 1) \cos \phi_2 + l_{3I} \sin \phi_2 \} \\ \beta_3 &= \frac{2n_2 V_{30}}{\pi L_2 n_3} \{ l_{1R} \cos \phi_3 + l_{1I} \sin \phi_3 \}, & \beta_4 &= \frac{2V_{20}}{\pi L_2} \{ l_{3I} \cos \phi_2 + (1 - l_{3R}) \sin \phi_2 \} \\ \beta_5 &= \frac{2n_2 V_{30}}{\pi L_2 n_3} \{ l_{1I} \cos \phi_3 - l_{1R} \sin \phi_3 \}, & \beta_6 &= \frac{4}{\pi C_3} \{ I_{31R} \cos \phi_3 - I_{31I} \sin \phi_3 \} \\ \beta_7 &= \frac{2n_3 V_{20}}{\pi L_3 n_2} \{ l_{3R} \cos \phi_2 + l_{3I} \sin \phi_2 \}, & \beta_8 &= \frac{2V_{30}}{\pi L_3} \{ (l_{1R} - 1) \cos \phi_3 + l_{1I} \sin \phi_3 \} \\ \beta_9 &= \frac{2n_3 V_{20}}{\pi L_3 n_2} \{ l_{3I} \cos \phi_2 - l_{3R} \sin \phi_2 \}, & \beta_{10} &= \frac{2V_{30}}{\pi L_3} \{ l_{1I} \cos \phi_3 + (1 - l_{1R}) \sin \phi_3 \} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Controller design procedure The control strategy proposed to regulate the output voltage of a TAB is described in this Section. A feedback proportional-integral (PI) controller is derived using the small-signal model obtained in the previous Section. Furthermore, the small-signal model is used to calculate a feed-forward (FF) term that compensates for the effect of the transformer currents on the voltage during load and source variations. The proposed control strategy sums the feedback and FF terms to improve the output voltage dynamic of the converter.

As mentioned before, the magnetic coupling in the HFT is one of the main challenges when controlling the TAB. This coupling issue is not considered explicitly in this control strategy. However, the control strategy proposed will be proven to be useful in reducing the effects of the coupling on the voltage response.

The proposed control strategy is based on the small-signal model previously presented. Specifically, on the dynamic equation that describes the change in the output ports voltages \hat{v}_{j0} which is rewritten for a generic port j in (21).

$$\frac{d\hat{v}_{j0}}{dt} = -\frac{\hat{i}_{j0}}{C_j} + \frac{4}{\pi C_j} (\hat{i}_{j1R} \sin(\phi_j) + \hat{i}_{j1I} \cos(\phi_j)) + \frac{4}{\pi C_j} (I_{j1R} \cos(\phi_j) - I_{j1I} \sin(\phi_j)) \hat{\phi}_j \quad (21)$$

Since the main goal of the control strategy is to regulate the voltage at the output ports v_{j0} using the phase-shift ϕ_j^{FB} , the disturbances coming from load changes and transformer current are removed from (21) using the superposition principle to obtain a simpler expression that relates the control and output variable as presented in (22).

$$\frac{d\hat{v}_{j0}}{dt} = \frac{4}{\pi C_j} (I_{j1R} \cos(\phi_j) - I_{j1I} \sin(\phi_j)) \hat{\phi}_j \quad (22)$$

Then, (22) is transformed into the Laplace domain to obtain the plant transfer function (24), which is used to design a FB controller that will provide the FB control action $\Delta\phi_j^{FB}$. A PI controller is designed using the pole placement method. The main parameters of the TAB are presented in Table 1.

$$\frac{\hat{v}_{j0}(s)}{\hat{\phi}_j^{FB}(s)} = \frac{4}{\pi C_j} \frac{(I_{j1R} \cos(\phi_j) - I_{j1I} \sin(\phi_j))}{s} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\hat{v}_{j0}(s)}{\hat{\phi}_j^{FB}(s)} = \frac{4}{\pi C_j} \frac{(I_{j1R} \cos(\phi_j) - I_{j1I} \sin(\phi_j))}{s} \quad (24)$$

Hence, the phase-shift $\hat{\phi}_j$ is replaced by the FB action $\hat{\phi}_j^{FB}$ in (22), and an explicit expression for the total control action $\hat{\phi}_j$ is provided in (25). Thus, the FF term could be defined as in (26), assuming that \hat{i}_{j0} , \hat{i}_{j1R} , and \hat{i}_{j1I} could be determined.

Table 1: TAB parameters

Parameter	Value
Port voltage: v_1, v_2, v_3	400, 400, 350 V
Port inductance: L_1, L_2, L_3	36.7, 36.5, 36.8 μ H
Port resistance: R_{s1}, R_{s2}, R_{s3}	135, 136, 139 m
Port capacitance: C_2, C_3	0.4, 0.4 mF
Switching frequency: f_s	20 kHz

$$\hat{\phi}_j = \hat{\phi}_j^{FB} + \frac{\hat{i}_{j0}}{C_j} - \frac{4}{\pi C_j} (\hat{i}_{j1R} \sin(\phi_j) + \hat{i}_{j1I} \cos(\phi_j)) \quad (25)$$

$$\hat{\phi}_j^{FF} = \frac{\hat{i}_{j0}}{C_j} - \frac{4}{\pi C_j} (\hat{i}_{j1R} \sin(\phi_j) + \hat{i}_{j1I} \cos(\phi_j)) \quad (26)$$

Finally, replacing (26) in (25), the total control action $\Delta\phi_j$ is presented in (27).

$$\hat{\phi}_j = \hat{\phi}_j^{FB} + \hat{\phi}_j^{FF} \quad (27)$$

In the implementation proposed here, the output currents and voltages i_{j0}, v_{j0} are assumed to be measurable. On the other hand, measuring the transformer currents and obtaining the decomposition of the real and imaginary parts of the harmonics of interest could be challenging. However, the GAM approach proves to be particularly relevant in addressing this task. The average model of the TAB presented in the previous Section is used to estimate the transformer currents, in particular the real and imaginary components of the first harmonic, to complete the FF terms.

The performance of the control strategy proposed is tested on a switching model based on the circuit presented in Fig. 1. The switching model was created in Simulink using the circuit parameters presented in Table 1. The parameters are taken from [16] and slightly modified to assess the control strategy when the TAB operates at different voltage levels on each port, which would allow connecting sources and loads with no voltage adaptation required. This should be one of the main advantages of topologies such as the TAB.

The mentioned characteristics of different voltage levels could be of interest when integrating multiple DER or microgrids whose voltage levels might not be homogeneous. In the mentioned applications, voltage regulation and stability are critical, regardless of the voltage levels.

The simulation starts with the TAB in the equilibrium operating condition. The proposed control strategy is tested considering three consecutive disturbances inducing a transient.

- Load at port 2 increases from 2 kW to 3 kW at time $t=0.1$ s.
- Load at port 3 increases from 1.5 kW to 3 kW at time $t=0.2$ s.

- The input voltage at port 1 increases from 400 V to 440 V at $t=0.3$ s.

Figure 3: Output voltage response under load and input voltage disturbances in port 2

Figure 4: Output voltage response under load and input voltage disturbances in port 3

These events are chosen in such a way that the control strategy is tested when disturbances occur in both output ports. The magnitude of the change is considered large enough for the load, considering that a sudden increase could occur in cases like EV charging connection in household applications, or microgrid interconnection reconfiguration leading to power flow changes. On the other hand, sudden voltage changes are not expected to happen, so a 10% disturbance is considered for the input voltage. The voltage response in port 2 and port 3 are shown in Fig. 3 and 4, respectively. The results achieved using the control strategy proposed (FB + FF), represented by the blue signal, are compared to the ones

obtained using a PI controller alone (FB), represented by the red signal. As expected, the proposed control strategy overcomes the performance of the FB controller alone, reducing the overshoot and settling time.

The effectiveness of the proposed control strategy is particularly evident for the voltage in port 3, during the event at $t=0.2$ s, when the larger disturbance takes place. In this case, the load current at port 3 is doubled, making the voltage drop more noticeable.

Sliding Mode Controller A suitable controller for a TAB converter must deal with its intrinsic nonlinearity and external disturbances in the input voltage and load demand. Moreover, it should ensure stability under any operating condition while it provides a fast transient response. Due to its switched nature, the TAB converter is considered a variable structure system (VSS). Therefore, it can be controlled using well-known techniques of sliding mode control (SMC) [20]. SMC has been largely applied to control the power DC-DC converters [21], [22], [23], [24]. The main advantages of SMC on conventional linear control are robustness, good dynamic response, and simple implementation.

To design an SMC, a reduced model of the TAB converter is derived as follows.

Reduced Model From (7), it can be seen that the power supply through the TAB DC-DC converter ports is coupled from each other. Decoupling the power flow would reduce the power error and complexity of the controller. Being that the output port 2 and port 3 are feeding a loads, the transferred power (P_{23}) between these ports is undesired and can be eliminated. A topology-level decoupling approach is adopted to deal with this issue [25,26].

As shown in (5) and (6), P_{23} is inversely proportional to inductance L_{23} , and for high values of L_{23} , P_{23} can be neglected. This operation would be possible if L_1 is omitted. In this way, power decoupling would be achieved (28). A simplified version of the equivalent TAB circuit referred to port 1 is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Simplified equivalent TAB DC-DC converter referred to port 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= \frac{n_{12}v_{in}v_2}{2\pi f_{sw}L_{12}}\phi_2\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_2|}{\pi}\right) + \frac{n_{13}v_{in}v_3}{2\pi f_{sw}L_{13}}\phi_3\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_3|}{\pi}\right) \\
 P_2 &= -\frac{n_{12}v_{in}v_2}{2\pi f_{sw}L_{12}}\phi_2\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_2|}{\pi}\right) \\
 P_3 &= -\frac{n_{13}v_{in}v_3}{2\pi f_{sw}L_{13}}\phi_3\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_3|}{\pi}\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

The switched model given in (2) is reduced as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{di_2}{dt} &= u_1 \frac{v_{in}}{L_{12}} - u_2 \frac{n_{12}v_2}{L_{12}} - \frac{r_{s12}i_2}{L_{12}} \\
 \frac{di_3}{dt} &= u_1 \frac{v_1}{L_{13}} - u_3 \frac{n_{13}v_3}{L_{13}} - \frac{r_{s13}i_3}{L_{13}} \\
 \frac{dv_2}{dt} &= -\frac{v_2}{C_2R_2} + \frac{u_2i_2}{C_2} \\
 \frac{dv_3}{dt} &= -\frac{v_3}{C_3R_3} + \frac{u_3i_3}{C_3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

where the control signals u_1 , u_2 and u_3 are square wave signals with the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1 &= \text{sign}(\sin(\omega_s t)) \\
 u_2 &= \text{sign}(\sin(\omega_s t - \phi_2)) \\
 u_3 &= \text{sign}(\sin(\omega_s t - \phi_3))
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Being that the average value of the transformer inductor current in a period is zero, the inductor dynamics can be ignored. Only the dynamics of the output filter capacitors are considered in the analysis [26].

Replacing u_2i_2 and u_3i_3 by I_2 and I_3 respectively, the switched model given in (29) is reduced to the following form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dv_2}{dt} &= -\frac{v_2}{C_2R_2} + \frac{I_2}{C_2} \\
 \frac{dv_3}{dt} &= -\frac{v_3}{C_3R_3} + \frac{I_3}{C_3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

where the current $I_2(= \frac{P_2}{v_2})$ and $I_3(= \frac{P_3}{v_3})$ are given by (32).

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &= \frac{n_{12}v_{in}}{\omega_s L_{12}}\phi_2\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_2|}{\pi}\right) \\
 I_3 &= \frac{n_{13}v_{in}}{\omega_s L_{13}}\phi_3\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_3|}{\pi}\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Replacing (32) into (31), the reduced model is described by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dv_2}{dt} &= -\frac{v_2}{C_2R_2} + \frac{n_{12}v_{in}}{\omega_s L_{12}C_2}\phi_2\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_2|}{\pi}\right) \\
 \frac{dv_3}{dt} &= -\frac{v_3}{C_3R_3} + \frac{n_{13}v_{in}}{\omega_s L_{13}C_3}\phi_3\left(1 - \frac{|\phi_3|}{\pi}\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Let us define the new control variables

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_1 &= \phi_2 \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_2|}{\pi}\right) \\ \mu_2 &= \phi_3 \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_3|}{\pi}\right)\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

Eq. 33 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dv_2}{dt} &= a_1 v_2 + b_1 \mu_1 \\ \frac{dv_3}{dt} &= a_2 v_3 + b_2 \mu_2\end{aligned}\quad (35)$$

where $a_1 = -\frac{1}{C_2 R_2}$, $b_1 = \frac{n_{12} v_{in}}{\omega_s L_{12} C_2}$, $a_2 = -\frac{1}{C_3 R_3}$ and $b_2 = \frac{n_{13} v_{in}}{\omega_s L_{13} C_3}$.

Design Procedure The design of two sliding-mode control laws is considered to control the power flow and regulate the output voltages in port 2 and port 3. The design of the sliding controller is split into two stages. First, one chooses a sliding surface that provides the desired asymptotic behavior when the system dynamics are forced to evolve on it. Then, the design of a control law that makes the phase trajectories are attracted by the sliding surface.

Let us choose two sliding surfaces defined in the following form

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_1 &= e_2 + k_{i1} \int e_2 \\ \sigma_2 &= e_3 + k_{i2} \int e_3\end{aligned}\quad (36)$$

in such a way that zero tracking error is guaranteed.

where $e_i = v_i - V_{ref,i}$ is the voltage error and $V_{ref,i}$ is the reference output voltage ($i = 2, 3$) and k_{i1} and k_{i2} are positive sliding coefficients. To ensure the existence of a sliding mode, a switching control law must be chosen so that the position of the system trajectory with respect to the sliding surface and its time derivatives have opposite signs, so that

$$\lim_{\sigma_i \rightarrow 0} \sigma_i \dot{\sigma}_i < 0 \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (37)$$

In order to make σ_i attractive and to satisfy the inequality of (37), reaching laws are introduced (38).

$$\dot{\sigma}_i = -\eta_i \text{sign}(\sigma_i) \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (38)$$

Applying the invariance property ($\sigma_i = 0$ and $\dot{\sigma}_i = 0$) and attractiveness (37), the control

laws μ_1 and μ_2 are computed:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1 &= -\frac{1}{b_1}((k_{i1} + a_1)v_2 - k_{i1}V_{ref2} + \eta_1 \text{sign}(\sigma_1)) \\ \mu_2 &= -\frac{1}{b_2}((k_{i2} + a_2)v_3 - k_{i2}V_{ref3} + \eta_2 \text{sign}(\sigma_2)) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

To Perform stability analysis, the *Lyapunov* function is defined as

$$V_i = \frac{1}{2}\sigma_i^2 \quad (40)$$

and its derivative with respect to time is as follows:

$$\dot{V}_i = \sigma_i \dot{\sigma}_i \quad (41)$$

Substituting μ_i (39) in $\dot{\sigma}_i$ (41) can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1 &= -\eta_1 |\sigma_1| \\ \dot{V}_2 &= -\eta_2 |\sigma_2| \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Therefore, \dot{V}_i must be strictly negative to ensure the asymptotic stability of the system. To achieve that, the coefficients η_1 and η_2 should be chosen positive. Numerical simulations are carried out using MATLAB/Simulink to assess the performance of the proposed controller. The block diagram of this latter is depicted in Figure 6. The parameters of the TAB converter under study are listed in Table 2.

Figure 6: Block diagram of Control scheme.

The proposed control strategy is tested under three consecutive disturbances. All disturbances last 0.02s and are listed below.

- The input voltage at port 1 increases 30% of its nominal value at $t = 0.04$ s.
- The load at port 2 increases 33.38% of its nominal value at $t = 0.07$ s.
- The load at port 3 increases 40% of its nominal value at $t = 0.08$ s.

Figures 7 and 8 depict the response of the TAB converter under variations of the input voltage and the loads at port 2 and port 3. It can be seen that the proposed controller can

Table 2: TAB Converter parameters

Parameter	Value
Rated power: P_1	3.5 kW
Port voltage: v_1, v_2, v_3	400, 400, 350 V
Port inductance: L_2, L_3	98, 148 μ H
Port capacitance: C_1, C_2, C_3	50, 50, 50 μ F
Switching frequency: f_s	50 kHz

guarantee an efficient sharing of power flow and a good tracking of reference voltages, with zero overshoot. Furthermore, good robustness against input voltage and load disturbances is guaranteed by this controller.

By analyzing Figure 9, we can see that the load voltage decreases when the input voltage increases. The proposed controller compensates for this voltage drop by reducing the phase shift and tracking the reference output voltage. Furthermore, the controller increases the phase shift when the output power demand increases.

Figure 7: Response of the TAB converter under nominal operation conditions: (a) Total power in each port, (b) Output voltages at Port 2 and Port 3.

Figure 8: Response of the TAB converter under input voltage and loads disturbances: (a) Total power in each port, (b) Output voltages at Port 2 and Port 3.

Figure 9: Waveforms of phase shift before and after three consecutive disturbances

4 Modeling and control of isolated MPC

In this chapter, modeling, control design and simulation of isolated MPC will be discussed. For this, the operation of various components making up the MPC are discussed first.

4.1 Definition of the topology

Inspired by the case study in Deliverable D1.1 [27], a schematic of a 3 port converter is shown in Fig. 10. The three ports are interconnected by a high-frequency DC-DC converter stage to provide both isolation between the ports as well as a dc-port connection point for integration of energy storage or photo-voltaic (PV) source. The modular multilevel converter to make up the medium voltage ac-ports are based on full-bridge (FB) modules.

Figure 10: Schematic of isolated MPC configuration

Different configuration of this isolation stage is possible and has been reviewed in Deliverable D1.1. An implementation that is chosen for investigation in this chapter which uses two alternatives of a multi-active bridge DC-DC converter as modular units is shown as an example in Fig. 11 (only one one-phase of the converter is shown). The number of active bridges per module can vary depending on the application. The ac-ports are made of series connection of cascaded H-bridge (CHB) cells to generate the required medium voltage levels. A DC-DC stage from the isolation stage can generate a dc-voltage at a level required by the source/load connected at the dc-port. As such, this configuration provides the advantages of modularity in voltage levels and number of ports, flexibility and reliability at a cost of higher system components.

4.2 Modeling and control of building units

The isolated MPC converter to be studied further consists of two ac-ports constituted by CHB-based MMC as shown in Fig. 12 and an isolation stage based on high-frequency DC-DC converters with multiple-active bridges (MAB) per module. The dc-port is also generated

Figure 11: Detailed schematic of two alternative implementation of one phase of the isolated MPC configuration.

from the isolation stage as indicated in Fig. 11, where an extra dc-dc stage can be added to obtain the voltage level to connect a source or load. The control and modeling of these components will be discussed briefly in this section.

4.2.1 Multilevel converter

The three-phase MMC is controlled using the classical approach of grid-following control on the ac-side in a synchronous dq -reference frame, where the various control loops will be described briefly here. Only parts of the control or modulation where there is a significant contribution from the work package will be detailed.

Phase-locked loop (PLL): This loop will generate the grid voltage angle such that the d -axis of the synchronous reference-frame aligns with the dq -voltage vector of the PCC. As such, d - and q -components of the current vector represent active- and reactive-power generating components for the control loops. For this loop, a proportional-integral (PI) controller is used to track the grid frequency and an extra integrator to generator the angle. The loop bandwidth is adjusted by tuning the proportional-integral (PI) gains [28].

Reactive-power or ac-voltage controller: This control loop generates the reference reactive-current to have a closed-loop control of the reactive power or the PCC voltage magnitude if it is needed as a grid-support requirement. In this investigation, an open-loop reactive-power control is adopted where the reference reactive-current is set directly

Figure 12: Detailed schematic of a 3-phase MMC with N CHB-based submodules.

based on the required reactive-power support and the measured grid voltage.

Active-power or dc-voltage controller: This control loop generates the reference active current. As the dc side of the converter is constituted by capacitors and any active-power exchange between the ac and dc side of the converter must be transferred to the other ports. This is achieved through the link provided by the isolation stage. In this work, the active-current reference is generated to control the sum of all capacitor voltages to a reference value. For this, a classical PI-controller is chosen. The active-power transfer will be controlled by the isolation stage as it will be described later. To improve the dynamic performance, a feed-forward term can be added to the generated reference active-current corresponding to the steady-state active power transfer from the MMC.

Current controller: This loop generates the reference converter voltage with a closed-loop current control where the reference currents are obtained from the outer loops. A PI-based controller with a grid-voltage feed-forward and a current cross-coupling compensation is implemented [28]. From the reference voltage and the sum of capacitor voltages in each phase, the modulation index for each phase is generated.

Individual and cluster cell balancing: In each phase, two low-level controllers are implemented. The first is to adjust modulation index based on the grid-voltage angle and the error between the reference and actual average capacitor-voltage of the SM (cluster-cell balancing). The second is to adjust the modulation index for each cell to balance the capacitor voltage of each cell in a phase-leg to the average cell-voltage of that particular phase (individual-cell balancing). This is similar to what algorithms such as sorting will do at the modulation stage and can be skipped in some cases where the modulation strategy provides a uniform utilization of the cells on average. This controller depends on the grid-voltage phase and the sign of the reactive-power exchange [29].

Modulation: With the normalized modulation index generated in previous loops, a phase-shifted pulse-width-modulation (PWM) with a certain carrier frequency is used to insert the FB sub-modules with either positive or negative capacitor voltage to generate the converter-voltage output. In this scheme, the SM are not bypassed and a bipolar switching is used for each submodule. This is a simple scheme and will generate about as many voltage levels as the number of submodules (SM) for each leg of the converter. With a higher carrier frequency, good harmonic performance can be achieved at a cost of higher switching loss. The use of phase-shifted PWM also means that sorting is not necessary to balance the capacitor voltages at the low-level control.

Another switching scheme that increases the number of output voltage levels is to use the bypass state of the SM. This means that the number of voltage levels can be doubled and this can be achieved by using a uni-polar switching scheme. The switching losses can be reduced by adopting a level-shifted PWM scheme. With this scheme, some SMs will be inserted much more than others and sorting is necessary to balance the capacitor voltages. However, in this work the level-shifted carriers assigned for each SM are interchanged among the SMs every carrier cycle to have all similar level of insertion and bypass over a fundamental period and hence sorting is not necessary. This is the preferred modulation strategy and this will be demonstrated in the next section.

4.2.2 High-frequency isolation transformer

A number of alternatives exist to realize the isolation stage using high-frequency based DC-DC converters. One of the options is to use Dual-active bridge modules combining each dc-side of the FB cells of the MMC. However, this will not provide the connection point

for creating a dc-port as well as it lacks the reliability of power flow for the particular sub-module. This can be alleviated by more active bridges and one of the options is to use triple-active bridge units where one of the active bridges can be used to create the dc-port as detailed in the previous chapter. The other option is to use more than one active bridge on both the primary and secondary side of the transformer to have more reliability for power transfer in case of a failure in the MMC sub-module or one of the active bridges in both the primary and secondary side. From the two alternatives of the multi-active bridge (MAB) setup in Fig. 11, the option similar to the one on the left is preferred based on reliability of power transfer and number of components.

Multiple active bridge DC/DC converter: DC-DC converters are important building blocks in medium-voltage converters. With multi-winding transformer connecting various inputs and outputs, a proper operation of the converter without unnecessary circulating power within the input and output sides (ensuring complete ac-operation without dc-bias on the transformer) as well as a good harmonic performance is of utmost importance. In this section, a proper operation of a 5 winding transformer based DC-DC converter with 2 inputs and 3 outputs as shown in Fig. 13 will be analyzed. This will be used as the module to make up the MV MPC setup as described in previous section. The impact of modulation scheme to improve harmonics content and a proper operation of the converter during normal operation and when one of the input/output ports fails will be discussed.

Figure 13: Schematic of a multi-active bridge DC-DC converter unit.

Description of the MAB: The schematic of a 5 active-bridges DC-DC converter module is shown in Fig. 13. The input side of the converter $V_{dc,1}$ and $V_{dc,2}$ are connected to two capacitor voltages of the FB-SMs of the MMC in ac-port 1 and the output side voltages $V_{dc,3}$ and $V_{dc,4}$ are connected to two capacitor voltages of the FB-SMs of the MMC in ac-port 2. The 3rd output $V_{dc,5}$ is connected to the dc-port with other similar outputs. Depending on the dc-voltage levels, the turns ratio of the windings can be adjusted and a further dc-dc

state can be added for full control of the dc voltage.

Control of the DC-DC converter: various alternatives exist for the control of the active-bridge DC-DC converters. Among these, the use of phase-shift modulation with a fixed 50% duty-cycle ac-voltage on the primary and secondary side of the transformer to operate the full-bridge converters is the simplest and the most common [8]. on the modulation scheme, two alternatives of bipolar and uni-polar switching schemes to generate a square wave and quasi-square wave ac-voltages on the primary side are implemented. The secondary side converters will be modulated similarly by applying a phase shift to the primary switching patterns base on the implemented control. The uni-polar scheme is used to minimize the total harmonic content in the input and output sides of the transformer. The harmonics content is improved with uni-polar switching without affecting the power transfer capability significantly and hence adds an advantage.

With ac-voltages generated on the input and output side of the transform and a fixed duty cycle used in the switching, the power transfer between the bridges is dictated by the phase-shift between the different bridges. With a chosen switching scheme, the converters on the primary side (converter 1 and 2) are operated with the same switching signals to minimize power transfer between them (circulating power). Similarly, the converters on the secondary side (Converer 3 and 4) are operated with the same switching patterns but phase-shifted from the pattern from primary side converters. This phase shift is dynamically adjusted to control the power transfer between primary-side and secondary-side converters. The maximum phase-shift is set to 90 degrees (a quarter of the switching cycle) so that an increase of its value leads to more power transfer [8].

With the converters 1, 2, 3 and 4 connected to the capacitor of the SMs of the MMC whose dc-voltages are controlled, the phase shift for converters 3 and 4 are adjusted through a PI controller to have a controlled power transfer between the bridges (power-control mode). With in the rating of the converters, a lose of one of the bridges in the primary or secondary sides or both still enable a power transfer between the primary and the secondary side. With the phase-shift controlling power, the lack of an active current controller in this scheme is the weak point in case of faults. Finally, the phase-shift for converter 5 from the switching pattern of converters 1 and 2 is adjusted through a PI-controller to obtain a controlled dc voltage, $V_{dc,5}$ (voltage-control mode).

4.3 Operation of the multiport converter

With the selected isolated MPC as described in the previous sections, operation in normal and abnormal conditions will be demonstrated in this section with detailed time-domain switching model of the isolated MPC implemented in the offline Typhoon simulation software.

4.3.1 Multiport converter configurations

The MPC topology for the investigation in this section is based a multi-active bridge DC-DC isolation stage as describe in the previous section. To demonstrate the operation of the MPC, an MMC with 4 FB-SMs on ac-port 1 and ac-port 2 is used. This means for each phase, two MABs as in Fig. 13 connecting the two ac-parts with isolation is implemented. The 5th winding of these MAB modules are connected together through a buffer capacitor to make up the dc-port. The nominal dc-voltage of the MMC capacitors is chosen as 1.67 kV and the DC port voltage is controlled to 400 V. The ac-ports have a nominal voltage of of about 5 kV. The winding ratios of the transformer $[n_1 : n_2; n_3 : n_4 : n_5]$ are chosen as $[1 : 1; 1 : 1 : 0.25]$.

4.3.2 Dynamic performance in normal conditions

The first set of results in this section shows normal operation of the converter in normal conditions. For this, the MMCs on the two ac-ports are connected to 3-phase grid with voltage of 5 kV. The MMCs provide a fixed 1 MVar reactive power support and the active power transfer between the ports is controlled. The active-power is controlled by the isolation stage and a controlled current source is connected at the dc-port to act as a load/generation connection point where the dc-voltage is controlled to a reference. This means that the amount of active power at ac-port 1 and ac-port 2 is automatically set by the dc-voltage controller on the two MMCs.

As it can be observed in Figs. 14 and 15, the level and direction of power flow is controlled with the capacitor voltage of all the sub-modules balanced and within limits. For varying power level in all parts, the dc-port voltage can be controlled close to the reference confirming a successful operation of the converter in normal conditions.

4.3.3 Impact of modulation strategy

Impact of modulation on the MMC and the DC-DC stage will be demonstrated separately in this section.

The MMC stage: As shown in Figs. 16 and 17, by using alternated level-shifted carriers, the number of output voltage levels can be improved. Alternating the carriers for each SM will enable all the SM to be inserted utilized for the same amount of time which avoids a dedicated sorting algorithm to balance the capacitor voltages as indicated in Fig. 15.

The DC-DC converter stage: the ac voltage and current outputs in one winding of a conventional phase-shifted bipolar operation of the MAB is shown in Fig. 18. By using a similar principle of operation and instead applying quasi-square wave voltages on the input and output side of the windings, the voltage waveforms and hence the current harmonics can be improved. The harmnic content and fundamental component of the ac voltages

Figure 14: power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through winings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter.

for varying the zero-level voltage is shown in Fig. 19. To minimize the total harmonic distortion, an angle of 45 deg with in half-cycle of the switching can be used and the results are displayed in Fig. 20. For this choice, the fundamental component of the voltage is not reduced much but the harmonics content for both the current and the voltage is improved. The small reduction in the fundamental voltage results in a little increase in the peak current but that is not significant compared to the improvement in the harmonics.

4.3.4 Impact of abnormal operation conditions

In this section abnormal conditions such as loss of one of the ac ports or the dc port, ac-voltage dips, unbalanced ac-grid operation and a loss of an active bridge or a SM in the

Figure 15: DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage.

MMC will be demonstrated to evaluate the robustness of the MPC. The loss of a SM in the MMC will also affect the power transfer through one of the windings of the MAB and the impact of this and how proper power transfer is achieved will be shown.

loss of a port: As shown in Fig. 14, the power delivered to ac-port 2 is the sum of the power transferred from ac-port 1 through the isolation stage and the generation from the dc-port. A loss of the dc-port will therefore not impact the operation of the MPC. However, if one of the ac-ports is lost, the power transfer through the isolation stage must be actively managed. For instance, if ac-port 1 is lost, the power delivered to that port should be zero to avoid loss of control and over- or under-voltage for the SM capacitors. This can be achieved by adjusting the power transfer through the isolation stage to fulfill the power balance and this requires active measurement of the consumption at all ports

Figure 16: Carrier (top) signals to generate the PWM output voltage (bottom) of the MMC for phase a.

Figure 17: Carrier (top) signals to generate the PWM output voltage (bottom) of the MMC for phase a.

and a detection mechanism for disconnection of the port. For instance, Figs. 21 and 22 demonstrates the power and voltage output of the MPC when ac-port 1 is lost at 0.55 sec

Figure 18: Bipolar switching MAB operation; input voltage to the winding 1 and 3 of the MAB (top), the corresponding differential voltage on the leakage inductance (middle) and the resulting current on winding 1 (bottom).

(grid disconnected) indicating the stable operation of the MPC in case of a loss of a port. In this demonstration, it is assumed that the detection and reference adjustment for power transfer through the isolation state is assumed instantaneous. Any related delays will result in the deterioration of the MPC performance.

3-phase voltage dip: Similarly, when a symmetric three-phase voltage dip happens in the ac-grid as in Fig. 23, depending on the ride-through strategy, the power exchange at the faulty port is managed through active management of the reference-active power and have a proper current limiting strategy. For instance, when a 3-phase voltage dip happens at ac-port 2, there was a 2 MW active power injection to the converter at 0.55 sec. To set the active-power injection to zero at this port (such as a case in strong voltage dip), the power transfer to port 1 should be managed based on the active power exchange at the dc-port. The results in Figs. 24 and 25 shows that the MPC operates well during the dip with a power exchange as required and the dc-port and SM capacitor voltages all within the range.

unbalanced grid-operation: For unbalanced grid-operation as in Fig. 26, a proper controller of the MMC including a negative sequence control is necessary to manage the

Figure 19: variation of harmonics content with zero voltage output for an angle of α for half the period; voltage waveform with uni-polar switching (top) and harmonics content (bottom).

power exchange at the ac-ports properly. With only the positive sequence control, the impact of unbalanced grid is to affect the proper operation of the converter through oscillation of the power exchange as well as oscillations and unbalances in the SM capacitor voltages as shown in Figs. 27 and 28 when an unbalanced grid happens at ac-port 2. Nevertheless, the converter works well for this grid without the need for changing of the power reference as there is enough remaining voltage to transfer the power. The addition of a negative sequence controller to improve the MPC performance can be part future tasks for the work package.

loss of an active bridge: Winding 2 of one MAB module is disconnected to test MPC operation in case of a SM outage or an active bridge failer. For this, winding 2 is discon-

Figure 20: Uni-polar switching MAB operation with $\alpha = 45$ deg; input voltage to the winding 1 and 3 of the MAB (top), the corresponding differential voltage on the leakage inductance (middle) and the resulting current on winding 1 (bottom).

ected for the time interval 0.2 - 0.22 sec. The power and current output in the primary side of this particular module is shown in Fig. 29. The results show that power transfer happens normally through the other active bridges with a reduction in total power transfer from the open bridge for the specified time interval. While the MAB modules work as intended, the internal operation of the MMCs is affected as shown in Figs. 30 and 31 due to a power unbalance through the capacitors of the SMs and the slow SM capacitor-voltage dynamics. This happens to the SM connected to the open winding (no power transfer for this capacitor) as well as the 2 SMs on the secondary side of this MAB module (only half the power is transferred). This unsymmetrical and unbalanced operation for the SM capacitors result in a deteriorated performance and this is one weak point of the isolated MPC operation.

Figure 21: power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through windings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter. ac-port 1 is disconnected at 0.55 sec.

Figure 22: DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage. ac-port 1 is disconnected at 0.55 sec.

Figure 23: Grid voltage when a 3-phase voltage-dip occurs at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec.

Figure 24: power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through windings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter; a 3-phase voltage-dip happened at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec and P_{ref} is set to $-P_{dc, port}$.

Figure 25: DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage; a 3-phase voltage-dip happened at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec and P_{ref} is set to $-P_{dc,port}$.

Figure 26: An unbalanced grid-voltage ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec.

Figure 27: power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through windings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter; an unbalanced grid-voltage at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec.

Figure 28: DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage; an unbalanced grid-voltage at ac-port 2 at 0.55 sec.

Figure 29: active power and current in the input side of the MAB module; winding 2 is open for 0.2 - 0.22 sec.

Figure 30: power transfer with in the MPC converter from top to bottom: total average-power transfer from primary to secondary side of the MAB through windings 1, 2, 3, and 4; power injected from the dc-port to the converter; power injected at ac-port 1 to the converter; and power injected to ac- port 2 from the converter. winding 2 of one MAB module open for 0.2 - 0.22 sec.

Figure 31: DC voltage levels of the MPC converter from top to bottom: SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1; SM capacitor voltages of MMC 2; average controlled SM capacitor voltages of MMC 1 and 2; controlled dc-port voltage. winding 2 of one MAB open for 0.2-0.22 sec.

5 Modeling and control of non-isolated MPC

5.1 Definition of the topology

The non-isolated MPC topology studied in the iPlug project has 2 AC/DC ports based on Modular Multilevel Converters (MMC) and 1 DC load which may be directly connected to the DC bus. The MPC has been studied in a system in which both MMCs are connected at the same AC grid by two identical feeders, because of the challenges that this system has when AC faults happen. Figure 32 shows an example of the studied system.

Figure 32: General schematic of the presented MPC.

5.2 Modeling and control of building units

The control of the presented non-isolated MPC is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: General schematic of the MPC control.

An MMC is a Voltage Source Converter (VSC) structure which could be an interesting solution in Medium Voltage (MV) and High Voltage (HV) grids. This converter uses sub-modules in series in which each of the sub-module has IGBTs in a half-bridge or full-bridge structure. Figure 34 shows a schematic of an MMC with half-bridge submodules.

To check the controls an averaged model is a solution that could reduce the computation time. The models can be averaged, as the power losses are small enough. Figure 35 defines the averaged model of an MMC.

Figure 34: Equivalent circuit of a three-phase MMC.

The switches are changed by a structure based on the voltage values, which are the outputs of the controller. Furthermore, depending on the saturation applied on each of the voltages of each sub-module, as shown in Section 5.2.9, it can be defined if the MMC is working as with half-bridge or full-bridge submodules.

The strategy followed to control the MMC is based on a change of variables in which there are used the additive and differential voltages and currents, as explained in the literature [1]:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} v_{diff}^j \simeq \frac{1}{2}(-v_u^j + v_l^j) \\ v_{sum}^j \simeq v_u^j + v_l^j \\ i_{sum}^j \simeq \frac{1}{2}(i_u^j + i_l^j) \\ R \simeq R_s + \frac{R_a}{2} \\ L \simeq L_s + \frac{L_a}{2} \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} v_u^j = -v_{diff}^j + \frac{1}{2}v_{sum}^j \\ v_l^j = v_{diff}^j + \frac{1}{2}v_{sum}^j \\ i_u^j = \frac{1}{2}i_s^j + i_{sum}^j \\ i_l^j = -\frac{1}{2}i_s^j + i_{sum}^j \end{array} \right. \quad (43)$$

where:

- v_{diff}^j : differential voltage, is approximately equal to the AC voltage at the midpoint of leg j.
- i_{sum}^j : additive current, represents the current that circulates from the upper to the lower arm of leg j.

Figure 35: Average model representation of an MMC [1].

- v_{sum}^j : additive voltage, which is approximately equal to the sum of the DC pole voltages.

If a steady-state analysis of the model and the AC and DC components is done [30], the following summary could be obtained for each of the current components and their uses.

Comp.	Freq.	Comp.	Use
i_s	AC	$+, -$	Current from the AC grid (Fortescue components).
		0	Equal to 0 due to three-wire connection.
	DC	α, β	Controlled to zero to prevent DC current flowing through the AC grid (Clarke coordinates).
		0	Equal to 0 due to three-wire connection.
i_{sum}	AC	$+, -$	Internal power exchange between upper and lower arms (Fortescue components).
		0	Controlled to zero to avoid AC distortion in the DC grid.
	DC	α, β	Internal power exchange between the legs of the converter (Clarke coordinates).
		0	Power flowing onto the DC grid.

Table 3: Converter current components and their uses.

In this report, an energy-based control strategy is used. The control architecture could be defined on two blocks: the energy control and the grid control. Unlike other VSCs, as 2-level converters, energy control is essential on MMCs, because if it is not controlled, the energy of the capacitors of the submodules would not be balanced. The calculation of the

references of each of the currents used to control both parts is essential, as each of them can be obtained from the AC part or the DC part.

The general control structure of the MMC is defined in Figure 36. As explained in the following lines, the calculation in the outer control of i_s^{q*} and i_{sum}^{0dc*} varies depending on the control strategy chosen (Classical or Crossed).

Figure 36: General control of an MMC.

A centralized control is used to ensure FRT capabilities in a wide range of faults, as the ports that participate in the control of the DC bus can be chosen. Apart from that, each MMC port has the following control blocks:

- PLL
- Reactive differential current calculation.
- Active differential current calculation.
- Inner current control.
- Energy calculation and control.
- Additive current reference calculation.
- Additive current control.
- Arms voltage calculation and modulation.

5.2.1 Centralized control

To ensure more robustness at the MPC, a controller apart from the control at each port is added, therefore, the contribution of each of the ports to the DC bus control can be decided, depending on its characteristics or faults location. The output obtained by this block is the active power reference value, which could be used to obtain i_{sum}^{0dc*} or i_s^{q*} , depending on the control strategy used. Figure 37 shows the structure.

Figure 37: Centralized control.

This control is based on a PI controller, where the active power reference output is distributed to the MMC control. The power distribution is defined based on the weighting parameters α_i , which represent the contribution of each port to the DC voltage regulation, i.e., to the power balance of the whole converter as the DC voltage is used as the scalar variable that indicates if the power balance is met. Therefore, the weighting parameters should ensure the condition

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \alpha_i = 1, \quad (44)$$

where $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the port number of the MPC and N is the total number of ports. A saturation is applied at the active power references to ensure that the signals are always inside the operation margin of the port. Besides, an anti-windup mechanism is also used to avoid the windup phenomenon [31, 32] if the port saturates.

Figure 37 shows that the centralized control scheme presented in this article regulates the DC bus voltage changing the value of P_i^* . The PI and the α_i gains tuning is critical to ensure that the error between $P_{ref_i}^*$ and P_i^* is small enough.

Algorithm 1 shows how to calculate α_i parameters. The code has been defined after doing different tests which take into account if charged DC power supply systems like batteries are available or if there exists a fault.

Algorithm 1: Algorithm to obtain the α_i parameter

input : Available active power of the charged DC power supply systems $P_{DC,i}$, nominal active power of the ports $P_{N,i}$, voltages seen by the ports V_i

output: Usage parameter α_i

```

1 begin
2   if a DC fault exists then
3      $\alpha_i = 0$ 
4   else
5     if a charged DC exchange system is connected then
6        $\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{DC,i}|}{\sum_{i=1}^N |P_{DC,i}|}$ ;
7     else
8       if a fault exists & there is a port with  $V_i \neq 0$  then
9          $\alpha_i = \frac{|V_i| \cdot |P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{i=1}^N (|V_i| \cdot |P_{N,i}|)}$ ;
10      else
11         $\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{i=1}^N |P_{N,i}|}$ ;

```

5.2.2 PLL

MMCs used in this paper are working in a grid-following mode, so a PLL is used to calculate the grid angle. The design used, also ensures that when a fault occurs, the angular velocity is frozen, so there could be avoided big peak values. Figure 38 shows the PLL architecture.

Figure 38: PLL.

5.2.3 Reactive differential current calculation

As Fault-Ride Through (FRT) is required, a calculation of injection current in case of fault is done. The control scheme is shown in Figure 39, based on other publications [33].

The characteristic curve used to calculate the injected current is based on the following piece-wise function:

$$\begin{cases} v_g^{low} \leq v_g \leq v_g^{high} \rightarrow & i_{inj} = \Delta i \frac{v_g^{high} - v_g}{v_g^{high} - v_g^{low}} \\ v_g \leq v_g^{low} \rightarrow & i_{inj} = \Delta i \\ v_g \geq v_g^{high} \rightarrow & i_{inj} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

Figure 39: Reactive differential current block.

Reactive current has priority in all cases except when there is a fault seen by both MMC ports. In this case, the port that has a bigger voltage prioritizes the active current (q-component):

Algorithm 2: Algorithm to choose the priority of q and d components.

input : Reactive current i_d , Active current i_q

output: Priority current of the terminal i_{pr} , Non-priority current of the terminal i_{non-pr}

1 **begin**

2 **if** an AC fault is seen by all the AC-DC terminals & no charged DC exchange systems & terminal with a voltage closer to its nominal value **then**

3 $i_{pr} = i_q$
 4 $i_{non-pr} = i_d$

5 **else**

6 $i_{pr} = i_d$
 7 $i_{non-pr} = i_q$

where:

$$-i_{max} \leq i_{pr} \leq i_{max}, \tag{46}$$

$$-\sqrt{i_{max}^2 - i_{pr}^2} \leq i_{non-pr} \leq \sqrt{i_{max}^2 - i_{pr}^2}. \tag{47}$$

5.2.4 Active differential current calculation

The active differential current calculation depends on the control strategy used (Classical or Crossed). So, both calculations are explained in detail in Sections 5.2.10 and 5.2.11.

5.2.5 Inner current control

From the reference currents calculated in Sections 5.2.3 and 5.2.4, there are obtained the differential voltages used to calculate the arms voltage values that have to be applied in each port. The Inner current control structure and parameters are based on the decoupled crossed structure already presented in the literature [34].

5.2.6 Energy calculation and control

To control the energy of each of the ports, the energy between leg a and b ($W_{a \rightarrow b}$), leg a and c ($W_{a \rightarrow c}$) and between each upper and lower arm in each of the legs ($W_{u \rightarrow l}^a, W_{u \rightarrow l}^b, W_{u \rightarrow l}^c$) are calculated. Each component is obtained as defined in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Arm energy calculation [2].

Also, total energy of the ports (W_t) is:

$$W_t = \sum_{j=a,b,c} W_u^j + W_l^j \tag{48}$$

All the references are 0, except for the total energy, in which case is:

$$W_t^* = 6 \frac{1}{2} \frac{C_{SM}}{N_{arm}} (V_t^{dc*})^2 \tag{49}$$

Figure 41 defines the energy balancing control, based on the literature [2].

Figure 41: Energy balancing control [2].

5.2.7 Additive current reference calculation

As Figure 36 shows, the additive current control has as references the additive currents. As the additive currents are a combination of AC and DC components, both references are calculated separately. AC currents are calculated as shown in Figure 42, based on the calculations already presented in the literature [1].

Figure 42: Additive current reference calculation [2].

A lead-lag compensator is added after the AC current reference calculation so that the AC components have a unity gain and no phase delay at the nominal frequency [30].

In the case of the DC additive currents, the references are calculated in $\alpha\beta 0$ frame. For the α and β currents calculation, there are used the following equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{sum}^{\alpha dc*} \\ i_{sum}^{\beta dc*} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3V_t^{dc}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \sqrt{3} & -\sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_{a \rightarrow b}^* \\ P_{a \rightarrow c}^* \end{bmatrix} \tag{50}$$

In the case of i_{sum}^{0dc*} , as it has been mentioned, it depends on the control structure chosen (Classical or Crossed), as explained in Sections 5.2.10 and 5.2.11.

As explained in [30], if AC additive current reference calculation is not changed, the behaviour of the MMC will be unstable during the fault. Therefore, when an AC fault happens, thanks to a fault detection mechanism based on the voltage value of each port, the AC additive current reference of each component is defined as 0.

When a DC fault happens, the i_{sum}^{0dc*} is defined as 0, so it is ensured that no current flows to the DC bus. Apart from that, the DC bus voltage is limited to 0.7 p.u. to avoid unstable behaviours.

5.2.8 Additive current control

Additive current control is based on PI controllers, which ensures a correct following of $\alpha\beta 0$ additive current components. Figure 43 shows the defined structure.

Figure 43: Additive current control [2].

5.2.9 Arms voltage calculation and modulation

Arms voltage calculation is done based on the change of variables that have been defined, so each arm voltage can be obtained.

In the case of the modulation, as Figure 44 shows, the modules are saturated between 1 and 0 (half-bridge) or between 1 and -1 (full-bridge).

Figure 44: Arms voltage calculation and modulation [2].

5.2.10 Classical control structure

With classical control strategy, the active differential current calculation is:

$$i_s^{q*} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{P^*}{u^q} \tag{51}$$

On the other hand, the calculation of i_{sum}^{0dc*} comes from the energy loop, as shown in Figure 45.

As Table 3 shows, i_{sum}^{0dc*} represents the current that is flown at the DC grid, so when an AC fault occurs, the total energy can be controlled. On the other hand, as i_s^{q*} , which is calculated from the DC bus, controls the grid voltage, the DC bus voltage would have worse behaviour than the energy. In the case of DC faults, the DC voltage would remain stable but total energy not, so this control would not be effective in the case of MPC and

Figure 45: Classical control i_{sum}^{0dc*} calculation [1].

DC faults.

5.2.11 Crossed control structure

With crossed control the calculation of i_s^{q*} and i_{sum}^{0dc*} is switched, as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Crossed control structure [1].

In this case, the i_{sum}^{0dc*} comes from the centralized control, so the DC bus current depends directly on maintaining the DC bus voltage as stable as possible. On the other hand, the total energy affects the differential voltages, so if there is an AC fault, there would not be control of the total energy. On the other hand, if a DC fault occurs, this control would ensure a control of the energy.

5.3 Modulation of the control signals

Averaged models are a useful tool to check that the controllers work as expected, however, to be more realistic is better to use switching models. The difference versus the averaged models is that switching models take into account the IGBTs of the MMCs, therefore, it is required to apply modulation.

In the literature are presented different modulation techniques for MMCs [3]. Figure 47 shows a summary of the different possible options.

Figure 47: Modulation techniques for a MMC [3].

In [35] an extensive explanation of MMC modulation techniques is done. When there are many levels, Nearest level modulation (NLM) is the best option, however, an algorithm is required to balance the SMs. On the other hand, PSC modulation is a technique which is difficult to apply with a lot of levels, but an algorithm to balance the SMs is not required [35]. Another possible option could be Space Vector PWM (SVPWM), but, this technique is very complex with more than 3 levels. As the designed MPC works with an MV application, the number of levels is limited, but bigger than 3, therefore PSC modulation is the technique that better suits the presented scenario and is being used in the switching models.

5.4 Impact of control strategies in abnormal conditions and AC faults

To check the effects of each of the control strategies, two different scenarios have been tested. In the first one, an MPC with two MMCs and 2 AC-balanced faults at different locations is studied (Figure 48).

In the case of AC faults, a DC port is not considered, as the simulation will be more complex and no relevant conclusions would be obtained.

The 3 more relevant scenarios studied are:

- Classical control and common balanced AC fault.
- Crossed control and common balanced AC fault.

Figure 48: System studied with AC balanced faults.

- Combined control and common balanced AC fault near classical control.

In the following sections, the results are shown.

Table 4 shows the used parameters for the simulation:

Parameter	Value
Nominal AC grid voltage, V_{AC}	4 kV
Nominal port converter power, S_n	5 MVA
Nominal DC bus voltage, V_{DC}	6.4 kV
Short Circuit Ratio, SCR	20
Number of submodules per arm, N_{SM}	4
Sub-module capacitance, C_{SM}	8e-3 F
P_1^*, P_2^*	0.6 p.u., -0.6 p.u.
Q_1^*, Q_2^*	0.4 p.u., -0.4 p.u.
R_g, L_g	0.7 R_{eq} , 0.7 L_{eq}
R_t, L_t	0.15 R_{eq} , 0.15 L_{eq}
R_1, L_1	0.15 R_{eq} , 0.15 L_{eq}
R_2, L_2	0.15 R_{eq} , 0.15 L_{eq}
R_l, L_l	0.01 p.u., 0.2 p.u.
R_a, L_a	0.01 p.u., 0.2 p.u.

Table 4: Parameters used for the simulations.

5.4.1 Classical control in both ports and an AC fault

In this case, the fault occurs near the common grid, so it is the most drastic scenario for the MPC.

Figures 49 and 50 show that DC voltage during the fault drops, as slowly as possible, however, the total energy of both ports is stable (having a peak at the beginning and end

Figure 49: Port 1 results and classical control.

of the fault). Also, the voltage of the arms is uncoupled during the fault because the AC additive currents are not controlled. After the fault, is required a transient to rebalance the capacitors of the submodules.

Figures 51 and 52 exhibit the results with the switching model, to ensure that the modulation is also working as expected.

5.4.2 Crossed control in both ports and an AC fault

To compare the control strategies, the fault is applied again near the common AC grid.

Crossed control strategy is used when an AC fault occurs, the results shown in Figures 53 and 54 are an inverse of the Classical control strategy. DC bus voltage is stable even during the fault, and a very small transient appears when the fault ends. However, the total energy drops as slowly as possible, so it is not controlled during the fault.

Figures 55 and 56 show the results with the switching model, to ensure that the modulation is also working as expected.

5.4.3 Classical control in one port with AC fault near and Crossed control on the other port

From previous results is concluded that a combination of both control strategies may be an interesting solution, especially if the port with crossed control is far enough from the fault.

The results from this scenario are:

Figure 50: Port 2 results and classical control.

Figures 57 and 58 show that the combination of both controls stabilizes more the voltage of the DC bus. Also, the port with Classical control (near the fault) has the energy controlled. The total energy of the port with Crossed control has a drop at the beginning of the fault, but later, it remains controlled.

The results with the switching model are not shown, as they do not give additional information.

5.5 Impact of control strategies in abnormal conditions and DC faults

The second scenario is a 3-port MPC, with a DC load directly connected to the DC bus (Figure 59).

MMCs with FB structure could ensure a DC fault-blocking capability using a switch to isolate the fault. Thanks to this characteristic, it has been checked that when a DC fault occurs, MPCs could give reactive power support, working as a STATCOM.

The parameters used for the simulation are the same as with AC faults testing.

5.5.1 Classical control

In the case of the classical control, DC fault blocking capability cannot be ensured, as i_{sum}^{0dc} is controlled by the total energy. Consequently, the total energy cannot be controlled during

Figure 51: Port 1 results, classical control and switching model.

the fault, which produces an unstable system.

5.5.2 Crossed control

With crossed control strategy α_i and i_{sum}^{DC0} variables are 0 during the fault. The additive 0 DC component, is defined as 0, so no current flows on the DC bus during the fault.

Figures 60 and 61 show that as there is a fault in the DC bus, active power and DC bus voltage cannot follow its references. However, the reactive power is controlled, working the MPC as a STATCOM.

Figure 52: Port 2 results, classical control and switching model.

Figure 53: Port 1 results and crossed control.

Figure 54: Port 2 results and crossed control.

Figure 55: Port 1 results, crossed control and switching model.

Figure 56: Port 2 results, crossed control and switching model.

Figure 57: Port 1 (Crossed) results and combined control.

Figure 58: Port 2 (Classical) results and combined control.

Figure 59: System studied with DC fault.

Figure 60: Port 1 results, crossed control and DC fault.

Figure 61: Port 2 results, crossed control and DC fault.

6 Application of grid-forming control in non-isolate MPC

6.1 Introduction

Grid-forming (GFM) control strategies allow voltage source converters (VSCs) to emulate an ideal voltage source for a given operating point; imposing a constant voltage magnitude and frequency and a low output impedance. GFM control can therefore establish an electric power system's voltage without depending on any other voltage [36]. This capability allows VSCs to support islanded operation when isolated from the grid and black-start re-synchronisation of areas that have experienced critical failures [37]. The voltage source behaviour also makes GFMs suitable to operate on weak (high impedance) grids where they can improve the operation of neighbouring grid-following devices [38,39].

Multiport power converters (MPCs) offer the aggregation and optimised utilisation of multiple energy ports in a single device and generally possess the objective of improving the stability and resilience of the distribution network (DN) that they connect to [40]. This overlaps with GFM control, which can be power- and energy-intensive and can be critical for grid stabilisation and the maintenance of supply in emergency conditions. As such, GFM control is deemed a key control approach that should be explored to maximise the value that MPCs can bring to the DN.

GFM controllers often use a droop relationship to achieve inherent load sharing [41]. The droop relationship can be arranged between active power P and frequency f and reactive power Q and voltage magnitude V , to resemble the coupling used on the wider power system. This configuration has been widely explored for use on transmission networks, where grid reactance X dominates over resistance R [42]. Alternatively, GFMs can be rearranged using a $P-V$ and $Q-f$ configuration, due to the dominance of R over X in low voltage (LV) microgrids [43].

There is less experience regarding the application of GFM controllers in the low to mid X/R ratio conditions (defined as X/R between 0.1 and 10 for the remainder of this chapter) that can be expected on DNs [43], where neither X nor R can be neglected.

The remainder of this section will focus on a $P-f$ $Q-V$ configured GFM controller due to the objective to integrate the MPC to the medium voltage (MV) DN (which is expected to possess an $X/R \geq 0$ and is operated in terms of the $P-f$ $Q-V$ couplings). Previous works have identified the following characteristics of GFM operation as X/R reduces towards $X \approx R$ and beyond:

- The reduction of steady-state active power transfer capability (which is true for all VSCs) [44].
- The increase of active and reactive power coupling, which translates to higher reactive

power requirement for a given active power operating point and lower damping [45].

- Varying impacts on converter stability [46,47].

6.1.1 Active and reactive power decoupling methods

A first consideration to mitigate PQ coupling on low to mid X/R conditions is to use a different GFM algorithm that is designed for the given grid conditions. Neither variations of the P, Q with f, V configuration offer significant improvement over one another as they both neglect one of X or R . Other GFMs with significantly different formulations, such as the virtual oscillator, could be explored [48]. A second consideration is the GFM’s inner loop. Open loop GFM configurations have been shown to be most effective at emulating an ideal voltage source [49], however, they do not control the PCC voltage and cannot impose a strict limit on the converter’s current. In contrast, a cascaded voltage and current control configuration controls the PCC voltage, offers strict current limiting ability, and may mitigate some cross-couplings via the cascaded loop configuration.

Beyond these initial control choices, several approaches have been proposed to mitigate the issues associated with GFM operation on low to mid X/R conditions. However, most appear to be associated with some significant compromise to the fundamental objectives that a GFM device might possess. Fig.62 provides a visual overview of the features of the different decoupling methods that are described in more detail below.

	Feature					
	Ability to decouple P and Q (in low X/R)	Impact on power sharing	Impact on power quality	Robust to variations in grid condition	Impact on voltage regulation	Requirement for grid information
Virtual reactance	Yellow	Green	Red	Yellow	Red	Yellow
-ve virtual resistance	Green	Green	White	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Voltage compensator	Green	White	White	Green	Red	Yellow
Virtual P and Q frame	Green	Red	White	Green	White	Red
Virtual V and ω frame	Green	Yellow	White	Green	White	Red

Figure 62: An overview of the features of approaches to decouple active and reactive power in low to mid X/R derived from the literature review. Green indicates a desirable characteristic, while yellow indicates mediocre, and red indicates undesirable. No colour is assigned if the approach does not have a clear impact on the given feature.

Virtual reactances have been proposed to increase the system’s X/R ratio [50]. This approach has been found to be unable to completely mitigate the coupling [46], can have an undesirable impact on power quality [51], and introduces a fundamental voltage deviation at the converter’s terminals that degrades voltage regulation [52]. Alternatively, a negative

virtual resistance can be imposed to offset the line resistance [53]. This approach is found to be more capable of mitigating the PQ coupling and reduces the associated voltage drop [46] but requires clear knowledge of the line resistance to achieve effective decoupling and risks decreasing the system's damping [54].

Other feedforward approaches have been proposed to adjust the angle and magnitude of the VSC's voltage based on the closed loop system's dynamic equations. For example, [45, 55] introduce compensators to mitigate the impact of non-negligible grid resistance and decouple the P and Q control. This approach is very effective at decoupling the control channels and is robust to errors in the X/R estimation, however, the decoupling allows grid voltage to vary significantly with the injection of P .

Finally, frame transforms have been proposed to reduce the impact of variable system impedances on PQ sharing by GFM droop controllers. A virtual power frame is proposed and developed in [56, 57], which transforms the active and reactive power signals to a modified frame using knowledge of the coupling impedance's angle. This approach appears to achieve good PQ decoupling and can be robust to variations in the grid condition but requires explicit knowledge of the coupling impedance and can have a negative impact on grid voltage regulation [41]. Additionally, the transformation to virtual active and reactive power diverts the GFM from controlling the physical powers that are injected to the grid [58]. A virtual voltage magnitude and frequency frame is proposed in [59], which transforms the voltage magnitude and frequency to maintain the ability to control the injected active and reactive powers. This approach is extended in [58] with a Q regulation strategy to improve the regulation of the grid's voltage. This strategy may be worth exploring in the future.

6.1.2 Considerations for a grid-forming multiport power converter

Beyond the operation in low to mid X/R conditions, there are several additional features that need to be considered to develop robust GFM control for DN applications and for its integration into a MPC. Current limitation is one key hurdle associated with the operation of GFM controllers. Current limitation is required to ensure that the current extracted from the VSC does not exceed its thermal capability, which is particularly difficult for GFMs whose grid-facing operation provides transient injections in response to grid disturbances [60]. Solutions are available to limit GFM's current e.g. [61–63], however, the optimal approach to balance effective current limitation with converter stability [64, 65] and grid-stabilising features [66] is still being explored.

A GFM's voltage-source nature will also complicate the energy balance of a MPC. Energy management systems have been developed for the integration of GFM control within multi-terminal DC systems [67, 68], which may be applied to MPCs. However, additional analysis

will be needed to optimise energy management strategy configurations and tuning for the MPC’s objectives.

Some examples of GFM MPCs have already been developed that present some aggregation of all of the above mentioned phenomena [48, 69, 70]. These MPCs are generally developed for low voltage applications.

Additionally, there is a need to analyse how GFM devices should be integrated into the DN, where the system is less capable of supporting bidirectional power flows and the introduction of grid-supporting injections from multiple locations could complicate network operation [71]. This integration and the value of GFMs will be assessed in later work following the development of a robust GFM MPC.

6.2 Methodology and modelling

This analysis aims to understand the GFM’s ability to achieve a MPC port’s fundamental objectives and is framed in terms of the multi-terminal soft open point (SOP) application, due to its relevance for MV levels. Some of the analysis will be transferrable for the other iPLUG applications that MPCs are deemed to provide value to. The MPC SOP (pictured in 63) is defined to connect two 20 kV feeders (each rated at 400 kVA) with a collocated distributed energy resource (DER) (100 kW and 400 V). The multiterminal SOP’s objectives include: the interconnection of different voltage levels, the improvement of the voltage profile to increase DER and DN utilisation [4], and the maintenance of fault current [72].

Figure 63: Single line diagram of the non-isolated multiport power converter with one grid-forming and one grid-following port connected to two AC feeders and the distant grid. The DC port integrates a battery.

To analyse the GFM’s ability to provide these fundamental objectives in the expected grid conditions, an ideal voltage source converter (VSC) with a GFM controller will be assessed in terms of a suite of metrics across a range of X/R conditions. The converter is represented in this section with a 2L VSC and not a modular multi-level converter due to the added complexity of the latter and the focus on the GFM control dynamics.

The steady-state power capability will be assessed to identify the theoretical range of operating points that the VSC may be capable of achieving. This is highly relevant to the SOP, which aims to minimise feeder overload by optimising power flows [73] but is

overlooked in recent analysis [47]. This can also inform wider operating characteristics such as reactive power requirements and implications for transient stability. The small-signal stability and dynamics will be assessed in terms of the linearised model's poles and zeroes. This can inform on the GFM controller's characteristics throughout the variation in grid conditions. Participation factors will be used to identify the relation between critical poles and system states. The small-signal characteristics will be related to the time-domain active power reference tracking. A brief introduction to a current-limiting strategy is also presented.

Following this fundamental analysis of control behaviour, the GFM is integrated into the non-isolated MPC described in Section ?? and subject to some initial analyses to identify the configuration's feasibility and future research paths. Future work will assess the GFM's wider operational features, its ability to stabilise the grid, and the operational hurdles associated with its integration to the MPC.

6.2.1 Ideal voltage-source converter with grid-forming control

An average VSC model with ideal DC energy source is connected to a representation of the DN as pictured in Fig.64. The simple model's parameters are detailed in Table 5. The VSC is sized to represent one of the 400 kVA ports of the SOP MPC. The VSC is integrated to the power grid via an LC filter, which is sized according to standard MV practices [45]. A Thevenin Equivalent voltage source and impedance is used to represent the power grid, where the voltage source is sized according to the DN voltage (20 kV) and the impedance is defined in terms of a representative inductance L_g and for a range of X/R ratios.

Figure 64: Line diagram of ideal VSC used for analysis of GFM control in low to mid X/R conditions.

The average VSC utilises a 1st order P-f droop with 2nd order Q-V droop, a current limiting virtual impedance (VZ), and a cascaded voltage and current controller. The following list justifies the choice of the control components:

- A P-f Q-V droop configuration is analysed as the MPC is being developed to operate on the MV grid where, although the resistance cannot be neglected, inductance tends to dominate [45].
- A 1st order P-f droop is used as it can offer improved transient stability compared to 2nd order configurations [74] and inertial support is rarely specified for in the DN.

Table 5: Base GFM tuning and ideal VSC model parameters.

Parameter		Value
Nominal voltage	V_n	kV 20
Synchronous frequency	ω_0	Hz 50
Grid inductance	L_g	PU 0.33
Rated power	S_n	kVA 400
Filter resistance	R_f	PU 0.02
Filter inductance	L_f	PU 0.05
Filter capacitance	C_f	PU 0.05
P-f droop coeff.	K_{pD}	PU 0.05
Q-V droop coeff.	K_{qD}	PU 0.05
Q-V droop time constant	τ_q	s 0.5
Voltage control proportional gain	K_{pVC}	0.0126
Voltage control integral gain	K_{iVC}	0.316
Current control bandwidth	ω_{CC}	Hz 100
Transient virtual inductance	L_{VZT}	PU 0.01
Transient virtual X/R	X/R_{VZT}	5

- A 2nd order Q-V is used to enable the setting of the voltage support speed, where immediate responses may complicate DN operation [37].
- A current limiting VZ is used to achieve current-limitation with improved transient stability compared to a hard current saturation approach [63].
 - A current limiting VZ is shown to possess the same small-signal characteristics as a transient VZ in [61], so is included to be interchanged with the threshold-based current limiting VZ for the linear analysis.
- A full cascaded voltage and current controller configuration is implemented in an attempt to improve the decoupling of active and reactive control channels in the low to mid X/R grid conditions and to offer a back-up current saturation approach to ensure the VSC's current limitations are not exceeded.

The full grid-forming control diagram is pictured in Fig.65 and the base tuning configuration is detailed in Table 5.

Electromagnetic transient time-domain model

The dynamic equations of the ideal VSC and grid system are modelled as described in [75]. This model is used to accurately resolve the non-linear time-domain dynamics of the system, to collect operating points for the initialisation and building of the small-signal model, and to verify the accuracy of the small-signal model.

Small-signal model

Figure 65: Grid-forming control diagram.

The small-signal model (SSM) is a linearised state-space representation of the EMT model described in Section 6.2.1. It accurately describes the behaviour of the VSC in the linear region around a given operating point. The SSM is implemented to allow the use of linear control theory tools to explore the stability, pole-state dependence, and dynamics of the VSC.

The SSM is implemented in the synchronous reference frame (SRF), where the q-axis is aligned with the a-phase of the abc frame signals. The SRF and transformations to and from the abc frame are described in [44]. The SSM used in this section includes three distinct SRFs (the grid frame, the PCC frame, and the internal converter frame), all rotating at the synchronous frequency, but separated by the phase angles of their corresponding voltages. This distinction allows the grid voltage to be disturbed to test the converter’s characteristics whilst maintaining accurate transfer of information while moving between the remaining frames.

The park and inverse park transforms, the electrical system variable (P , Q , and V) calculations, and the measurement sensors need to be linearised to express the VSC and grid system in the state-space domain. The non-linear systems and the methods used to linearise them are detailed in [75].

The remaining subsystems already exist in the EMT time-domain model (TDM) in a linear

form. All of the subsystems can now be combined in a state-space representation in terms of state, input, output, and corresponding matrices. The Matlab state-space representation is utilised to describe the subsystems in terms of these components and the overall VSC and grid system can be built by connecting these subsystems in terms of inputs and outputs.

The SSMs are verified with respect to the non-linear EMT TDM to ensure their accuracy. Figs. 66 to 68 picture the TDM and SSM responses to equivalent input disturbances for discrete points across the X/R range of interest for both rectification and inversion operating points. The tested systems include the MIMO active and reactive power responses to an active power reference step (Fig.66), and the MIMO admittance (which pictures active and reactive grid current component responses to active (Fig.67) and reactive (Fig.68 voltage component steps). No results are pictured for the rectification systems in the extreme low $X/R = 0.22$ conditions as the corresponding $P_{OP} = 0.9 \text{ PU}$ operating point does not exist, which will be discussed in more detail in Section 6.3.1. All of the SSM systems show acceptable accuracy with respect to the EMT TDM.

Figure 66: Verification of MIMO SSM active and reactive power responses to a 1 % step in the active power reference as the grid’s X/R ratio and the converter’s initial power operating point are varied.

The SSM is used to provide information on the system’s poles and zeros (which describe the system’s stability and dynamics), pole-state participation factors, as well as planned fu-

Figure 67: Verification of MIMO SSM current responses to a 1 % step in the active grid voltage component as the grid’s X/R ratio and the converter’s initial power operating point are varied.

ture frequency-domain analysis (which can be useful to describe the converter’s behaviour across a range of timescales). The pole-state participation factors are calculated using Equation 52, where V are the right eigenvectors and W are the left eigenvectors of the linearised system that contains $i = 1 : I$ eigenvalues (λ) and $j = 1 : J$ states.

$$PF_{i,j} = \frac{W_{i,j}V_{i,j}}{W_i^T V_i} \tag{52}$$

6.2.2 Non-isolated multiport power converter with grid-forming control

The GFM VSC port described in Section 6.2.1 is integrated into the non-isolated MPC (detailed in Section ??) at AC port 1 (pictured in Fig.63). The GFM uses the current limiting virtual impedance instead of the transient virtual impedance to limit the current to $I_{max} = 1.1 \text{ PU}$.

The current limiting virtual impedance is configured so that current limitation begins above a threshold current value $I_{thresh} = 1 \text{ PU}$ and becomes stronger as the current increases towards I_{max} for the case of a three-phase fault occurring at impedance $Z_l = R_l + jXR * R_l$ from the converter. The proportional gain K_{pVZ} is tuned according to Equations

Figure 68: Verification of MIMO SSM current responses to a 1 % step in the reactive grid voltage component as the grid's X/R ratio and the converter's initial power operating point are varied.

53 to 57 [61], where $V_{pk} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}V$.

$$a_{VZ} = 1 + XR_{VZ}^2 \quad (53)$$

$$b_{VZ} = 2R_l(1 + XR_{VZ}XR) \quad (54)$$

$$c_{VZ} = R_l^2(1 + XR^2) - \frac{V_{pk}^2}{I_{max}^2} \quad (55)$$

$$R_{VZ} = \max(-b_{VZ} \pm \frac{\sqrt{b_{VZ}^2 - 4a_{VZ}c_{VZ}}}{2a_{VZ}}) \quad (56)$$

$$K_{pVZ} = \frac{R_{VZ}}{I_{max} - I_{thresh}} \quad (57)$$

The other AC port uses the same GFL control as detailed in Section ?? but is adapted to represent the 2-level VSC configuration, instead of the MMC model. Accordingly, this GFL port only includes the PLL, reactive and active current differentials, and inner current controller.

The DC battery port is represented using a DC RL circuit, as pictured in Fig.69, where the modulated voltage dV_{Batt} is set using cascaded DC voltage and current controllers. The control strategy is pictured in Fig.70. This DC voltage control allows the two AC ports to

follow given active power dispatch references, without consideration of the wider MPC's operation. The DC voltage control gains are tuned using Equations 58 and 59.

$$K_{pVDC} = \frac{2\pi C_{DC}\zeta_{VDC}}{t_{VDC}} \quad (58)$$

$$K_{iVDC} = \frac{C_{DC}(\frac{2\pi}{t_{VDC}})^2}{2} \quad (59)$$

The current control gains are tuned using Equations 60 and 61.

$$K_{pIB} = \frac{L_{Batt}}{t_{IB}} \quad (60)$$

$$K_{iIB} = \frac{R_{Batt}}{t_{IB}} \quad (61)$$

Figure 69: Battery circuit diagram.

Figure 70: DC battery port control diagram.

The DC link is modelled as a capacitor C_{DC} , whose current I_{DC} is the summation of the DC currents of each of the MPC's ports (pictured in Fig.71). The capacitor is sized according to Equation 62. The battery's contribution to the DC current $I_{DC,Batt}$ is calculated using Equation 63, while the DC currents of each of the AC ports $I_{DC1,2}$ is calculated using Equation 64.

$$C_{DC} = \frac{2t_{DC}S_n}{V_{DC}^2} \quad (62)$$

$$I_{DC,Batt} = \frac{dV_{Batt}I_{Batt}}{V_{DC}} \quad (63)$$

$$I_{DC1,2} = \frac{\sum E_{1,2} I_{s1,2}}{V_{DC}} \quad (64)$$

Figure 71: DC link circuit of the non-isolated MPC.

All of the parameters of the MPC model with the GFM port are provided in Table 6.

Table 6: Model parameters for the non-isolated MPC with GFM port.

Parameter	Value		
Nominal DC voltage	V_{DCn}	kV	1
DC capacitor time constant	t_{CDC}	s	0.05
Battery resistance	R_{Batt}	Ω	1.8
Battery inductance	L_{Batt}	H	0.11459
DC voltage control time constant	t_{VDC}	s	0.3
DC voltage control damping	ζ_{VDC}		0.707
DC current control time constant	t_{IB}	s	0.001
Resistance between converter and fault	R_l	PU	$R_g * 0.15$

6.3 Impact of grid reactance to resistance ratio

The following section details the results of the initial analysis of the ideal VSC model pictured in Fig.64 using the EMT TDM and SSM to advance the understanding of GFM control behaviour in the low to mid X/R conditions.

6.3.1 Steady-state power transfer

Two voltage sources separated by some impedance can be used to describe the power transfer between a VSC and the grid (relating to Fig.64). The active power transferred between these sources is described by Equation 65.

$$P_e = \frac{EV R_t \cos(\delta) - E^2 R_t + EV X_t \sin(\delta)}{R_t^2 + X_t^2} \quad (65)$$

Figure 72 shows the significant impact that the X/R ratio has on Equation 65 and therefore the ability of a converter to transfer active power, particularly for rectification (in this case positive power and angle). For the grid conditions described in Table 5, the converter becomes unable to rectify $P = 0.9$ PU on $X/R < 1.47$. In comparison, the converter can achieve the inversion of $P = -0.9$ PU until $X/R < 0.22$. Additionally, Figure 72 depicts the

Figure 72: Steady-state active and reactive power transfer as a function of converter angle as grid X/R ratio varies.

movement of converter operating point to higher angles to achieve a given active power transmission as X/R reduces, which has implications on the system's transient stability.

The reactive power transferred between the two voltage sources is defined in Equation 66.

$$Q_e = \frac{-EV R_t \sin(\delta) - E^2 X_t + EV X_t \cos(\delta)}{R_t^2 + X_t^2} \quad (66)$$

Fig.72 depicts this equation's variation as grid X/R varies. Despite the reduction of peak values as X/R reduces, a converter will be driven to operate at higher (positive or negative) angles to achieve a given active power transfer, which can increase the associated reactive power transfer. This describes the increased active and reactive power coupling that has been noted to be experienced by GFM converters in DNs and will also have an impact on the converter's available capacity to transmit active power.

The findings from this analysis of the steady-state power curves is verified using the EMT TDM of the GFM converter in Fig.73. The EMT TDM is dispatched for a set of increasing magnitude active power references (both rectification and inversion). The TDM closely agrees with the steady-state power transfer curves, showing that a rectification $P = 0.9 \text{ PU}$ operating point exists for $X/R = 1.47$ but not for $X/R = 1$ and that an inversion $P = -0.9 \text{ PU}$ operating point exists for $X/R = 0.22$ but not for $X/R = 0.15$.

6.3.2 Small-signal stability and dynamics

The following section describes the analysis of the small-signal linear VSC and grid system model throughout the X/R sweep. The sweep has been carried out for the range of X/R conditions that a converter can achieve a rectification $P = 0.9 \text{ PU}$ ($X/R = 1.47$ to 10) and an inversion $P = -0.9 \text{ PU}$ operating point ($X/R = 0.22$ to 10). However, the results are only presented for the inversion operating point as both sweeps exhibit similar results but

Figure 73: Verification of active power transfer capability on different grid X/R ratios using the EMT TDM.

across a larger range in the case of the inverter.

Figure 74: Participation factors of the linearised closed loop VSC and grid system for an initial inversion operating point $P_0 = -0.9 \text{ PU}$, on three example grid X/R ratios.

Fig.74 depicts the participation factors calculated for the closed loop linearised model of the VSC and grid system for three X/R conditions using Equation 52. The system’s poles are pictured on the x-axis and the states are arranged on the y-axis. The participation factor describes the impact that varying a given state has on each pole. The higher the

participation factor the more dependent the pole is on the state. A participation factor threshold of 0.2 is applied to highlight the key pole-state dependencies. Poles are covered in a grey fill if they exist outside of the critical area, defined as: pole damping $\zeta < 0.2$ and real part of the pole $Re(\lambda) \geq -100$.

The key variations in pole-state dependency include:

- Poles 11,12 have no dependence on any state greater than 0.2 in low X/R conditions before becoming more dependent on the PCC voltage measurement state (DUdu) on higher X/R s.
- Poles 16,17 experience a change from sole dependence on voltage control states (xUqd) in low X/R to a shared dependence for mid X/R and ultimately arriving at a sole dependence on angle generation state (xThc) for high X/R .
- Pole 18 exhibits an inverse change from sole dependence on angle generation (xThc) to a shared dependence to a sole dependence on voltage control-related virtual impedance states (xdVZT) as X/R increases.

Fig.75 depicts different areas of a pole-zero map of the VSC SSM throughout the X/R sweep. Poles are depicted with crosses and zeroes are depicted with filled circles, each of which are coloured according to the grid X/R condition. The map ignores poles 1,2; 9,10; and 21,22 due to their large negative real parts (all with magnitude greater than 9000) that do not move significantly throughout the sweep.

Several poles experience significant movement throughout the X/R sweep, however, there is a mixture of stabilising and destabilising variations. Current measurement and control dependent poles 5,6 (Fig.75 a) and 14 (Fig.75 d)) and voltage control dependent poles 11,12 (Fig.75 b)) move significantly towards the RHP as X/R increases.

In contrast, some of the poles that exist closest to the RHP, poles 16,17 (Fig.75 c)) and 18 (Fig.75 e)), exhibit stabilising movement away from the RHP as X/R increases. These are the poles that experience the dependence swapping from angle generation to voltage control (and vice versa) throughout the sweep.

Two of the linearised system's zeroes experience significant movement towards the right half of the map throughout the sweep, one of which cross into the RHP for $X/R \geq 0.32$. The remaining zeroes maintain relatively constant location throughout the sweep.

Fig.76 depicts the time-domain active and reactive power responses of the VSC to an active power reference step of -10 % (from an initial operating point $P_{OP} = -0.9$ PU) across the range of X/R conditions. Several features of the response vary depending on the X/R condition.

The direction of the steady-state reactive power response varies from negative for $X/R = 0.22$, to positive for $X/R = 0.32$ to 2.15, before reverting to negative for $X/R \geq 3.16$. This

Figure 75: Pole-zero map of the linearised model for an initial inversion operating point $P_0 = -0.9 \text{ PU}$ as X/R varies. Subplot a) exhibits the widest scale (excluding neglected modes), b) exhibits a zoom to mid-scale, c) exhibits a zoom to narrow scale, d) focuses on poles 13,14, and e) focuses on poles 18, 19, and 20.

Figure 76: Time-domain active and reactive power responses of the converter in response to an active power reference step of -10 % for an initial inversion operating point $P_0 = -0.9 \text{ PU}$ and a range of grid X/R ratios.

change in direction can be understood by tracking the high, mid, or low negative angle required to invert the initial active power for each condition, the increase in negative angle to follow the power reference step, and by tracking between these angles on the reactive power-angle curve pictured in Fig.72.

The response speed of both the active and reactive power signals increases with X/R . This agrees with the participation factor analysis, which showed the angle generation (and therefore power control) to depend highly on pole 18 in very low X/R . As X/R increases, the participation factor analysis showed the power control to begin depending more on poles 16,17, which exist further from the RHP. Following the change in dependence, the movement of poles 16,17 away from the RHP further supports the reduction of the active power tracking speed.

Additionally, the reactive power response exhibits non-minimum phase zero (NMPZ) behaviour on all of the grids with $X/R \geq 0.32$. This behaviour worsens as X/R increases. The NMPZ behaviour agrees closely with the movement of the zero pictured in Fig.75.

6.3.3 Current-limiting for the grid-forming converter

The current limiting virtual impedance is integrated into the base GFM control strategy. Fig.77 pictures the current and voltage behaviour of the EMT model of the ideal GFM VSC with the current-limiting virtual impedance during a three-phase fault. The GFM is dispatched to invert $P = -0.5 \text{ PU}$. The fault occurs at $t = 1 \text{ s}$ and is cleared following 0.25 s . The VSC's current magnitude minus the maximum allowed current I_{max} is pictured to show the efficacy of the current limiting method. To remain within the VSC's capacity, the signal should not exceed zero.

The virtual impedance effectively limits the VSC's current to the limit during the fault, however, is not able to contain the current within this limit during the transient periods when the fault occurs and is cleared. This is due to the virtual impedance's consideration only of the current magnitude. The GFM VSC is capable of re-synchronising with the grid following the fault for the pictured nominal voltage conditions.

Figure 77: Verification of the GFM's current limiting capability using the EMT TDM.

Fig.78 pictures the ideal GFM VSC tracking increasing rectification and inversion power references following the implementation of the current limiting virtual impedance for a range of X/R conditions. The VSC exhibits a similar ability to achieve the full range of

theoretical inversion operating points, however, it cannot achieve the rectification of $P=1$ PU for $X/R = 1.47$. This represents a reduction in the feasible operating range (compared to that pictured in Fig.72) following the addition of the current limiting virtual impedance.

Figure 78: Verification of the GFM with current-limiting virtual impedance's active power transfer capability on different grid X/R ratios using the EMT TDM.

Advanced current limiting approaches

Additional strategies have been proposed that consider the current's phase as well as magnitude [76], which should be explored for more robust current limitation compared to the strategy assessed throughout this Chapter. Another downfall of this approach is the requirement to tune the current limiting virtual impedance in terms of a given fault condition (e.g Equations 54 and 55), which can drive either the under-utilisation of the converter's capacity or poor current limiting.

Additionally, the balance between GFM behaviour and plant protection should be considered, where a fault-ride through algorithm may override the VSC's current contribution to zero, in which case the PCC voltage would be completely unsupported and fall to zero during the fault.

6.4 Initial analysis of the grid-forming multiport power converter

The non-isolated MPC configuration is integrated together, including the GFM AC port with current limiting virtual impedance, the GFL AC port, and the DC battery port. Fig.79 depicts the active power of the three ports as the GFM and GFL ports are dispatched to equal inverting and rectifying power levels, respectively. The battery controls the DC voltage.

The MPC is capable of transferring 1 PU of active power between the two AC ports for all of the X/R conditions, apart from the $X/R = 0.22$. This represents an improvement compared to the ideal transfer capacity of a single VSC, where rectification to 1 PU was

only possible for $X/R \geq 1.47$. The reason for the improved stability as well as the source of instability on $X/R = 0.22$ both represent potential future analysis paths. The battery output is non-zero despite the equal (opposite) AC port active power transfers due to the reactive power contribution of the GFM port. Similar behaviour is observed (but is not pictured) when the GFM port is dispatched to rectify and the GFL port to invert.

Figure 79: Verification of the MPC’s active power transfer capability on different grid X/R ratios using the EMT TDM. This case dispatches the GFM port to invert power and the GFL port to rectify power.

Fig.80 focuses on the behaviour of the GFM port of the MPC during the final power reference step in Fig.79 for the stable X/R conditions. Similar, but not identical, time-domain properties are exhibited for the GFM port of the MPC compared to those of the ideal GFM depicted throughout Section 6.2.1. The active power tracking speed slows and the non-minimum phase zero behaviour reduces as X/R decreases. The non-minimum phase zero behaviour appears to be present in both the active and power responses, whereas the ideal VSC only exhibited this behaviour in the reactive power response. This phenomena should be explored in more detail with consideration of the parallel GFL port and overall MPC’s operation.

Figure 80: Focus on the time-domain properties of the MPC during the final power step pictured in Fig.79.

The MPC’s GFM port response to a three-phase fault on the AC grid is pictured in Fig.81.

The GFM and GFL ports are dispatched to invert and rectify $|P| = 0.5 \text{ PU}$, respectively and the fault is identical to that described in 6.3.3. The current-limiting virtual impedance exhibits similar behaviour as a part of the MPC as it did for the ideal GFM VSC (limiting the current to the maximum capacity during the fault but not during the transients following the disturbance and clearance). However, the transient responses of the GFM and GFL ports following the fault's clearance pull all of the energy from the DC capacitor before the battery voltage controller can respond. This drives the destabilisation of the entire MPC. Faster DC voltage controller speeds were briefly explored but did not allow the stable operation of the MPC during initialisation.

Figure 81: The MPC's current-limiting ability following a three phase fault on the AC grid for a case where the GFM port is inverting $P = -0.5 \text{ PU}$ and the GFL is rectifying $P = 0.5 \text{ PU}$.

Fig.82 depicts the response of the GFM MPC during the same three-phase fault but for GFM and GFL ports that are dispatched to $P = -0.1 \text{ PU}$ and $P = 0.1 \text{ PU}$, respectively. In this case the battery is capable of sufficiently controlling the DC voltage to allow the AC ports to re-synchronise with the grid and continue normal operation. The source of instability in the $|P| = 0.5 \text{ PU}$ case and interaction with the DC voltage controller should be explored further. Additionally, the choice and features of different energy management strategies is a key research path to further develop a robust GFM MPC.

Figure 82: The MPC’s current-limiting ability following a three phase fault on the AC grid for a case where the GFM port is inverting $P = -0.1PU$ and the GFL is rectifying $P = 0.1PU$.

7 Conclusions

Modeling and control of multi-port power converters (MPCs) for medium voltage application has been discussed in this report, where two distinct MPC topologies, isolated and non-isolated alternatives have been considered. The various components that make up the converters are described and the operation of the converters in different operation conditions have also been demonstrated.

In chapter 3, the DC-DC converter that constitute the isolation stage of the isolated-MPC topology is described. Both dual- and triple-active bridge units are discussed and the case of triple-active bridge converter has been studied in detail. Two modeling and control strategies have been depicted and derived. First, a control strategy for the triple active bridge has been proposed. The generalized average model has been proved useful in the design and implementation of the control strategy proposed, avoiding the measurement and decomposition of the transformer currents needed to calculate the feed-forward terms on the control action. The control strategy is compared to a PI controller alone, showing an improvement in the overshoot and settling time of the voltages under load and source variations. Furthermore, a non-linear control strategy based on the sliding-mode control was proposed. A reduced order model was used in the controller derivation, and the control strategy showed a good performance against changes in the input voltage and output load.

In Chapter 4, the overall operation of isolated MPC is discussed. Adding up on the studies made in the previous chapter, the MPC is constituted by multi-active bridge based DC-DC converter for the isolation stage and a multilevel converter based on cascaded H-bridge cells to make up medium voltage ac ports. Control of multi-active bridge DC-DC converter with control of both power exchange between primary and secondary sides as well as dc-voltage control on one of the secondary side ports that will make up the dc-port of the MPC has been developed. A control and configuration that can withstand a loss of an active bridge is demonstrated. In addition, uni-polar based modulation strategy for the multi-active bridge DC-DC converters that improves the harmonic content has been propose. The method still inherits the simplicity and robustness of the conventional phase-shifted modulation of active-bridge converters. A mixed level- and phase-shifted modulation strategy for the multilevel converter that improves switching losses but improves harmonic content has been proposed. The modulation scheme enables no need of sorting to balance the sub-module voltages. The operation of a fully isolated MPC converter with good dynamic performance during normal and faulty conditions has been demonstrated and the challenges of this topology in terms of sub-module capacitor voltages during an unsymmetrical operations is also shown.

In Chapter 5, non-isolated MPC has been presented as a solution in Soft Open Point applications with normal and abnormal conditions (AC and DC faults). AC and DC fault

management techniques have been explained, which ensure that the MPC has FRT capabilities. Two different control strategies have been studied in the outer control of the AC-DC ports: classical and crossed control. With classical control and AC faults, the total energy is stable, but the DC bus voltage cannot be controlled. The inverse results are obtained with crossed control. With DC faults and classical control, unstable results are obtained, as the total energy cannot be controlled. With the crossed controller a STATCOM behavior of the MPC is ensured. Therefore, depending on the application required by the MPC, the most suitable controller can be selected.

GFM controllers are suitable to provide stabilizing functionality to the grid and may be better positioned to use the aggregated energy of MPCs than conventional two-port converters. However, there are many research questions that need to be answered to first achieve their secure operation and then optimize their behavior for DN applications. In Chapter 6, the impact of grid X/R conditions on an ideal GFM VSC's behavior is highlighted. Further work aims to implement a robust control methodology to optimize the characteristics of the GFM controller for a multi-terminal SOP's objectives. A simple current-limiting strategy was implemented to ensure the GFM strategy did not exceed the VSC's current capacity. The approach achieved reasonable performance, but was not able to contain the current during the initial periods of a disturbance. More robust current limiting approaches should be explored to ensure the safe operation of a GFM port within a MPC. Finally, a GFM port was integrated into the non-isolated MPC discussed in the previous chapter to provide an initial assessment of the feasibility of a GFM MPC for a SOP application. The MPC's behavior was partially described by the ideal GFM VSC analysis; however, additional operational features require analysis. The energy management strategy is a key area that should be explored, particularly due to the energy-intensity of the GFM port. Additionally, the behavior of the GFM port and wider MPC should be verified with increasing accuracy, such as control- and hardware-in-the-loop modeling. All of the analysis should consider the benefits and complications associated with introducing GFM controller to DNs.

References

- [1] E. Sanchez-Sanchez, E. Prieto-Araujo, A. Junyent-Ferre, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Analysis of mmc energy-based control structures for vsc-hvdc links," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 6, pp. 1065–1076, 9 2018.
- [2] E. Sánchez-Sánchez, "Energy-based control schemes of modular multilevel converters for hvdc," 2020.
- [3] A. António-Ferreira, C. Collados-Rodríguez, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Modulation techniques applied to medium voltage modular multilevel converters for renewable energy integration: A review," pp. 21–39, 2 2018.
- [4] K. S. Fuad, H. Hafezi, K. Kauhaniemi, and H. Laaksonen, "Soft Open Point in Distribution Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 210 550–210 565, 2020, conference Name: IEEE Access.
- [5] L. Ferreira Costa, G. De Carne, G. Buticchi, and M. Liserre, "The smart transformer: A solid-state transformer tailored to provide ancillary services to the distribution grid," vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 56–67.
- [6] H. Zhang, Y. Wang, and Z. Chen, "Topologies of isolated multiport converters for dc grid applications: A review," in *2022 IEEE 13th International Symposium on Power Electronics for Distributed Generation Systems (PEDG)*, 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [7] L. F. Costa, G. Buticchi, and M. Liserre, "Quad-active-bridge dc–dc converter as cross-link for medium-voltage modular inverters," vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 1243–1253.
- [8] L. F. Costa, "Modular power converters for smart transformer architectures," Ph.D. dissertation, Universitätsbibliothek Kiel, 2019.
- [9] L. F. Costa, G. De Carne, G. Buticchi, and M. Liserre, "The smart transformer: A solid-state transformer tailored to provide ancillary services to the distribution grid," *IEEE Power Electronics Magazine*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 56–67, 2017.
- [10] H. Shadfar, M. Ghorbani Pashakolaei, and A. Akbari Foroud, "Solid-state transformers: An overview of the concept, topology, and its applications in the smart grid," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, vol. 31, no. 9, p. e12996, 2021.
- [11] M. A. Hannan, P. J. Ker, M. S. H. Lipu, Z. H. Choi, M. S. A. Rahman, K. M. Muttaqi, and F. Blaabjerg, "State of the art of solid-state transformers: Advanced topologies, implementation issues, recent progress and improvements," *Ieee Access*, vol. 8, pp. 19 113–19 132, 2020.

- [12] R. W. De Doncker, D. M. Divan, and M. H. Kheraluwala, "A three-phase soft-switched high-power-density dc/dc converter for high-power applications," *IEEE transactions on industry applications*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 63–73, 1991.
- [13] S. Shao, L. Chen, Z. Shan, F. Gao, H. Chen, D. Sha, and T. Dragičević, "Modeling and advanced control of dual-active-bridge dc–dc converters: A review," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 1524–1547, 2021.
- [14] F. D. Esteban, F. M. Serra, and C. H. De Angelo, "Control of a dc-dc dual active bridge converter in dc microgrids applications," *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, vol. 19, no. 8, pp. 1261–1269, 2021.
- [15] H. Qin and J. W. Kimball, "Generalized average modeling of dual active bridge dc–dc converter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 2078–2084, 2011.
- [16] S. Okutani, P.-Y. Huang, and Y. Kado, "Generalized average model of triple active bridge converter," in *2019 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 5554–5560.
- [17] S. R. Sanders, J. M. Noworolski, X. Z. Liu, and G. C. Verghese, "Generalized averaging method for power conversion circuits," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 251–259, 1991.
- [18] P. Purgat, S. Bandyopadhyay, Z. Qin, and P. Bauer, "Continuous full order model of triple active bridge converter," in *2019 21st European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE'19 ECCE Europe)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. P–1.
- [19] S. Bacha, I. Munteanu, A. I. Bratcu *et al.*, "Power electronic converters modeling and control," *Advanced textbooks in control and signal processing*, vol. 454, p. 454, 2014.
- [20] V. I. Utkin, "Sliding mode control design principles and applications to electric drives," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electronics*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 6783–6800, 2008.
- [21] H. Sira-Ramirez, "Sliding motions in bilinear switched network," *IEEE Trans. Cir. Sys.*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 919–933, 1987.
- [22] R. Venkataramanan, A. Sabanovic, R., and S. Cuk, "Sliding mode control of dc–dc converters," in *IEEE Ind. Electronics Conf.* IEEE, 1985, pp. 22–30.
- [23] P. Mattavelli, L. Rossetto, and G. Spiazzi, "Small-signal analysis of dc–dc converters with sliding mode control," *IEEE Trans. Power Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 69–102, 1997.

- [24] L. Martinez-Salamero, J. Calvente, R. Giral, A. Poveda, and E. Fossas, "Analysis of a bidirectional coupled-inductor cuk converter operating in sliding mode," *IEEE Trans. Circit Syst.*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 355–363, 1998.
- [25] F. Wu, K. K. Wang, and J. Su, "Tab series-resonant dc-dc converter and multi-phase-shift based global optimization modulation," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 13, pp. 6783–6800, 2022.
- [26] P. Koochi, A. J. Watson, J. C. Clare, T. B. Soeiro, and P. W. Wheeler, "A survey on multi-active bridge dc-dc converters: Power flow decoupling techniques, applications, and challenges," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 16, p. 5927, 2023.
- [27] S. Harrison, B. Soltowski, A. Alvarez, A. F. Abdelfattah, C. H. Munoz, A. Pepiciello, M. Beza, M. Mañe and O. Bellmunt, "iPLUG - Deliverable D1.1: Overall requirements, specifications, KPI, and use case definitions," 2023.
- [28] M. Beza, "Power system stability enhancement using shunt-connected power electronic devices with active power injection capability," Ph.D. dissertation, Chalmers University of Technology, 2015.
- [29] E. Behrouzian, "On control of cascaded H-bridge converters for STATCOM applications," Ph.D. dissertation, Chalmers University of Technology, 2017.
- [30] E. Prieto-Araujo, A. Junyent-Ferré, C. Collados-Rodríguez, G. Clariana-Colet, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Control design of modular multilevel converters in normal and ac fault conditions for hvdc grids," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 152, pp. 424–437, 11 2017.
- [31] S. Galeani, S. Tarbouriech, M. Turner, and L. Zaccarian, "A tutorial on modern anti-windup design," *European Journal of Control*, vol. 15, pp. 418–440, 2009.
- [32] P. Hippe, *Windup in Control*, 2006.
- [33] M. D. Hernandez, O. E. Mas, M. C. Mane, E. P. Araujo, and O. G. Bellmunt, "Fault ride through control of multiport converter for distribution grids," vol. 2022-October. IEEE Computer Society, 2022.
- [34] A. Egea-Alvarez, A. Junyent-Ferré, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, *Active and Reactive Power Control of Grid Connected Distributed Generation Systems in Modeling and Control of Sustainable Power Systems*. Springer, 2012.
- [35] K. Sharifabadi, L. Harnefors, H. Nee, S. Norrga, and R. Teodorescu, *Design, Control and Application of Modular Multilevel Converters for HVDC Transmission Systems*. Wiley, 10 2016.

- [36] J. Rocabert, A. Luna, F. Blaabjerg, and P. Rodríguez, "Control of Power Converters in AC Microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 11, pp. 4734–4749, Nov. 2012, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics.
- [37] "GC0137: Minimum specification required for provision of GB grid forming (GBGF) capability (formerly virtual synchronous machine/VSM capability)," Warwick, UK, Nov. 2021.
- [38] R. H. Lasseter, Z. Chen, and D. Pattabiraman, "Grid-Forming Inverters: A Critical Asset for the Power Grid," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 925–935, Jun. 2020, conference Name: IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics.
- [39] A. Quedan, W. Wang, D. Ramasubramanian, E. Farantatos, and S. Asgarpoor, "Behavior of a High Inverter-Based Resources Distribution Network with Different Participation Ratios of Grid-Forming and Grid-Following Inverters," in *2021 North American Power Symposium (NAPS)*, Nov. 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [40] Z. Huang, D. Zhou, L. Wang, Z. Shen, and Y. Li, "A Review of Single-Stage Multiport Inverters for Multisource Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 6566–6584, May 2023, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics.
- [41] N. Bhatt, R. Sondhi, and S. Arora, "Droop Control Strategies for Microgrid: A Review," in *Advances in Renewable Energy and Electric Vehicles*, S. P., N. Prabhu, and S. K., Eds. Singapore: Springer, 2022, pp. 149–162.
- [42] Y. Lin, J. H. Eto, B. B. Johnson, J. D. Flicker, R. H. Lasseter, H. N. Villegas Pico, G.-S. Seo, B. J. Pierre, and A. Ellis, "Research Roadmap on Grid-Forming Inverters," National Renewable Energy Lab. (NREL), Golden, CO (United States), Tech. Rep. NREL/TP-5D00-73476, Nov. 2020.
- [43] C. Li, S. K. Chaudhary, M. Savaghebi, J. C. Vasquez, and J. M. Guerrero, "Power Flow Analysis for Low-Voltage AC and DC Microgrids Considering Droop Control and Virtual Impedance," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 2754–2764, Nov. 2017.
- [44] A. Egea-Alvarez, A. Junyent-Ferré, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Active and Reactive Power Control of Grid Connected Distributed Generation Systems," in *Modeling and Control of Sustainable Power Systems: Towards Smarter and Greener Electric Grids*, L. Wang, Ed. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2012, pp. 47–81.

- [45] Y. Laba, A. Bruyère, F. Colas, and X. Guillaud, "PQ Decoupling on Grid-Forming Converter Connected to a Distribution Network," in *2022 IEEE 13th International Symposium on Power Electronics for Distributed Generation Systems (PEDG)*, Jun. 2022, pp. 1–6, iSSN: 2329-5767.
- [46] T. Wen, X. Zou, X. Guo, D. Zhu, L. Peng, and X. Wang, "Feedforward Compensation Control for Virtual Synchronous Generator to Improve Power Decoupling Capability," in *2019 14th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications (ICIEA)*, Jun. 2019, pp. 2528–2533, iSSN: 2158-2297.
- [47] X. Gao, D. Zhou, A. Anvari-Moghaddam, and F. Blaabjerg, "Analysis of X/R Ratio Effect on Stability of Grid-Following and Grid-Forming Converters," in *2023 IEEE 17th International Conference on Compatibility, Power Electronics and Power Engineering (CPE-POWERENG)*, Jun. 2023, pp. 1–6, iSSN: 2166-9546.
- [48] M. Awal, M. Rashed Hassan Bipu, S. Chen, M. Khan, W. Yu, and I. Husain, "A Grid-Forming Multi-Port Converter using Unified Virtual Oscillator Control | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore."
- [49] K. V. Kkuni, S. Mohan, G. Yang, and W. Xu, "Comparative assessment of typical control realizations of grid forming converters based on their voltage source behaviour," Jun. 2021, arXiv:2106.10048 [cs, eess].
- [50] P. C. Nakka and M. K. Mishra, "Droop characteristics based damping and inertia emulation of DC link in a hybrid microgrid," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 1044–1052, 2020, eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1049/iet-rpg.2019.0691>.
- [51] G. Hou, F. Xing, Y. Yang, and J. Zhang, "Virtual negative impedance droop method for parallel inverters in microgrids," in *2015 IEEE 10th Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications (ICIEA)*, Jun. 2015, pp. 1009–1013.
- [52] U. B. Tayab, M. A. B. Roslan, L. J. Hwai, and M. Kashif, "A review of droop control techniques for microgrid," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 76, pp. 717–727, Sep. 2017.
- [53] X. Zhang, J. Liu, and T. Liu, "Virtual negatively resistive output impedance for power sharing among paralleled inverters in microgrid," in *8th International Conference on Power Electronics - ECCE Asia*, May 2011, pp. 1809–1812, iSSN: 2150-6086.
- [54] A. Rodríguez-Cabero, J. Roldán-Pérez, and M. Prodanovic, "Virtual Impedance Design Considerations for Virtual Synchronous Machines in Weak Grids," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1477–1489,

- jun 2020, conference Name: IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics.
- [55] Y. Laba, A. Bruyère, F. Colas, X. Guillaud, and B. Silvestre, "Operating Grid-Forming Control on Automotive Reversible Battery Charger," in *2021 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*, Oct. 2021, pp. 1–6, iSSN: 1938-8756.
- [56] K. De Brabandere, B. Bolsens, J. Van den Keybus, A. Woyte, J. Driesen, and R. Belmans, "A Voltage and Frequency Droop Control Method for Parallel Inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 1107–1115, Jul. 2007, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics.
- [57] T. Wu, Z. Liu, J. Liu, S. Wang, and Z. You, "A Unified Virtual Power Decoupling Method for Droop-Controlled Parallel Inverters in Microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 5587–5603, Aug. 2016, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics.
- [58] Y. Li and Y. W. Li, "Power Management of Inverter Interfaced Autonomous Microgrid Based on Virtual Frequency-Voltage Frame," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 30–40, Mar. 2011, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid.
- [59] —, "Decoupled power control for an inverter based low voltage microgrid in autonomous operation," in *2009 IEEE 6th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference*, May 2009, pp. 2490–2496.
- [60] J. Matevosyan, B. Badrzadeh, T. Prevost, E. Quitmann, D. Ramasubramanian, H. Urdal, S. Achilles, J. MacDowell, S. H. Huang, V. Vital, J. O'Sullivan, and R. Quint, "Grid-Forming Inverters: Are They the Key for High Renewable Penetration?" *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 89–98, Nov. 2019, conference Name: IEEE Power and Energy Magazine.
- [61] A. D. Paquette and D. M. Divan, "Virtual Impedance Current Limiting for Inverters in Microgrids With Synchronous Generators," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 1630–1638, Mar. 2015, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications.
- [62] L. Huang, H. Xin, Z. Wang, L. Zhang, K. Wu, and J. Hu, "Transient Stability Analysis and Control Design of Droop-Controlled Voltage Source Converters Considering Current Limitation," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 578–591, Jan. 2019, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid.

- [63] B. Fan, T. Liu, F. Zhao, H. Wu, and X. Wang, "A Review of Current-Limiting Control of Grid-Forming Inverters Under Symmetrical Disturbances | IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore," Jul. 2022.
- [64] G. Wu, B. Zhao, X. Zhang, S. Wang, A. Egea-Alvarez, Y. Sun, Y. Li, D. Guo, and X. Zhou, "Impact of Non-Minimum-Phase Zeros on the Weak-Grid-Tied VSC," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1115–1126, Apr. 2021.
- [65] T. Qoria, H. Wu, X. Wang, and I. Colak, "Variable Virtual Impedance-Based Overcurrent Protection for Grid-Forming Inverters: Small-Signal, Large-Signal Analysis and Improvement," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 3324–3336, Sep. 2023, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid.
- [66] H. Wu and X. Wang, "Small-Signal Modeling and Controller Parameters Tuning of Grid-Forming VSCs With Adaptive Virtual Impedance-Based Current Limitation," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 7185–7199, Jun. 2022.
- [67] Q. Zhang, "Control of Multi-Terminal VSC-HVDC Systems for Combined AC/DC Systems to Improve Power System Dynamic Performance - ProQuest."
- [68] S. I. Nanou, O. D. Tzortzopoulos, and S. A. Papathanassiou, "Evaluation of an enhanced power dispatch control scheme for multi-terminal HVDC grids using Monte-Carlo simulation," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 140, pp. 925–932, Nov. 2016.
- [69] I. Roasto, A. Rosin, and T. Jalakas, "Power electronic interface converter for resource efficient buildings," in *IECON 2017 - 43rd Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Oct. 2017, pp. 3638–3643.
- [70] N. Mдини, S. Skander-Mustapha, and I. Slama-Belkhodja, "Control with grid forming of a PV-BESS system for a 4-wire residential microgrid," in *2021 12th International Renewable Energy Congress (IREC)*, Oct. 2021, pp. 1–6, iSSN: 2378-3451.
- [71] T. Reimann, B. O. Winter, and W. Heckmann, "Need for grid-forming units in the distribution grid and their impact on protection, automation and control," Jun. 2023.
- [72] W. Cao, J. Wu, N. Jenkins, C. Wang, and T. Green, "Operating principle of Soft Open Points for electrical distribution network operation," *Applied Energy*, vol. 164, pp. 245–257, Feb. 2016.
- [73] S. K. Chaudhary, J. M. Guerrero, and R. Teodorescu, "Enhancing the Capacity of the AC Distribution System Using DC Interlinks—A Step Toward Future DC Grid," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1722–1729, Jul. 2015, conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid.

- [74] D. Pan, X. Wang, F. Liu, and R. Shi, "Transient Stability of Voltage-Source Converters With Grid-Forming Control: A Design-Oriented Study," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1019–1033, Jun. 2020, conference Name: IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics.
- [75] S. L. Harrison, "Advancements in converter-based frequency stability : recommendations for industrial applications," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, UK, Aug. 2023.
- [76] A. Narula, P. Imgart, M. Bongiorno, M. Beza, J. R. Svensson, and J.-P. Hasler, "Voltage-Based Current Limitation Strategy to Preserve Grid-Forming Properties Under Severe Grid Disturbances," *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 4, pp. 176–188, 2023, conference Name: IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics.

Annex

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